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Report on progress in beam diagnostics for hadron LINACs

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ABSTRACT

Section 3 of this Report covers the subject of Deliverable 8.1 (Progress in beam diagnostics for Hadron Linacs). Sections 3.1 to 3.3 summarize the three International Workshops organised on this specific subject, and Section 3.4 presents some general conclusions on the status of this field and on possible future developments. In the Appendix, detailed descriptions of the three Workshops concerned are given.

ARIES Work Package 8 aims for transfer of knowledge and standardisation of equipment across the European Research Infrastructures making use of beam instrumentation and diagnostics for particle accelerators. In total, 11 International Workshops were organized with 32 to 239 delegates (maximum for a remote workshop). Financial support for visits of scientists was covered in total for eight weeks.

While in the initial Work Plan it was foreseen to produce as a Deliverable four separated Reports, one for each of the Tasks/sub-sets of diagnostic equipment, during the execution of the project it turned out the number of intercorrelations and crossed references between the four areas was so large that it was more effective to produce a single report, with four Sections each devoted to one of the Tasks/Deliverables.

ARIES Consortium, 2021

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors, please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>.

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Executive summary

To meet the demands of new accelerator facilities, novel beam instrumentation and diagnostics methods are required. Beam instrumentation deals with versatile topics of applied physics and various technologies. The network 'Advanced Diagnostics at Accelerator' (ARIES-ADA) focused activities at various laboratories to initialize collaborations on a formal or, in most cases, informal basis. As a methodology, topical workshops related to one actual subject was chosen; moreover, the exchange of personnel between accelerator laboratories and universities is covered financially. Eleven topical workshops were organized; all workshops had participants from America, Asia and Europe. In three of these workshops, ARIES-ADA acts as a co-sponsor, leading to increasing contributions. Eight of these topical workshops were organized as a high-light event; each covers a topic that is not discussed in such detail at conferences and contributed significantly to a knowledge transfer between experts in various fields.

Eight of the workshops were executed as an in-person meeting between May 2017 and June 2019; depending on the subject, the number of delegates varied from 32 to 84. Personal contact is the key issue for sustainable collaborations, and those workshops contribute significantly to their initialization. The workshop duration was between one and three full days. The financial budget of ARIES-ADA was used to cover part of the costs of the workshops.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic initialized travel restrictions started in spring 2020, three workshops were organized as remote events between three and five half-days. The number of registrants was higher than the in-person meetings and increasing contributions.

In addition to the workshops, the budget was used to finance personnel exchanges for three scientists and duration between two and four weeks. In particular, early-stage scientists benefitted significantly. Several further visits were planned but could not be realized due to the travel restrictions that showed up at the end of 2019.

In contrary to the planned initially categories related to the different types of accelerators (hadron LINAC, hadron synchrotrons, circular light sources and linear light sources), it turned out that it is much more efficient to discuss in a common report the challenges related to various diagnostics methods, gaining from the synergy between the communities. Consequently, one more comprehensive deliverable report instead of four separate reports has been produced. The workshop content is shortly described in the main text, and detailed summaries of each workshop are attached as an appendix.

The subject of Deliverable 8.1 is therefore covered in Section 3 of the present Report.

1. Introduction

To meet the demands of new accelerator facilities, novel beam instrumentation and diagnostics methods are required leading to the permanent development of beam instruments. Versatile technologies are used based on many aspects of applied physics. The knowledge transfer between accelerator laboratories, universities, and industry is the focus of the ARIES work-package 8 network activity called ‘Advanced Diagnostics at Accelerator’ (ARIES-ADA). As the methodology, the organization of topical workshops related to one dedicated topic was chosen, offering the possibility of in-depth discussion on one subject not covered at typical conferences in such detail. A further aim is to initialize or intensify collaboration between the laboratories and strengthen the contact to industry for joint developments and efficient usage of available human resources. The industry is a relevant partner and contributed to several scientific talks the workshops.

Initially, it was planned to divide the work package into four tasks, namely related to hadron LINACs (Task 2 led by GSI), hadron synchrotrons (Task 3 led by CERN), circular synchrotron light source (Task 4 led by ALBA) and linear FEL light sources (Task 5 led by DESY). During the work-package execution, it turned out that this is not an efficient classification as most of the actual workshop topics comparably concerned several tasks. Due to this change of perspective, the planned initially individual Deliverable Reports D8.1 to D8.4 are now combined in a lengthy report covering the entire work-package program.

Eleven topical workshops were organized; all workshops had participants from America, Asia and Europe. Table 1 contains the compilation of the workshops, including the links to the INDICO site and some basic numbers cornering the duration, number of participants etc. For three of these workshops, ARIES-ADA acts as a co-sponsor, allowing for an increase of contributions. Eight of these topical workshops were organized as a high-light event; each covers an actual topic, which is not covered in such detail at typical conferences. The program ARIES-ADA contributed significantly to the knowledge transfer between experts in various fields in science and technology. In particular, engineers participated in those workshops, who usually are not contributing to regular conferences.

Eight of the workshops were executed as in-person meetings between May 2017 and June 2019; depending on the subject, the number of delegates varied from 32 to 84. Personal contact is the key issue for sustainable collaborations, and those workshops contribute significantly to their initialization. The workshop duration was between one and three full days. The financial budget of ARIES-ADA was used to cover part of the workshops costs and contributed to the travel costs of the workshop attendees. This allows for the participation of not only physicist but also engineers and technical personnel and people from outside of Europe where the home institutes might now be able to cover the full travel cost.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic initialized travel restrictions starting in spring 2020, three workshops were organized as remote workshops with a duration of between three and five half-days. The number of registrants was higher than in-person meetings, namely 49, 205 and 239. About 100 people were connected simultaneously during the presentation sessions for the last two workshops. The easier access without travels disabled a wider variety of contributions presented to a broader audience.

Personal discussions were still possible, in particular, when separated 'breakout rooms' were prepared beforehand by the workshop organizers.

Table 1: Compilation of topical workshops organized within the frame of ARIES-ADA; the columns are the date, main organizer, location of the workshop, title (linked to workshop INDICO-site), number of delegates the task which is mainly concerned and co-organizing tasks.

#	Date	Org. & location	Title of workshop	# Part.	main task	Contr. task
1	22-24 May 2017	GSI Darmstadt	Simulation, Design & Operation of Ionization Profile Monitors	33	2	3
2	29-30 Jan. 2018	ALBA & DESY Barcelona	Emittance Measurements for Light Sources and FELs	37	5	4
3	14-16 May 2018	CERN & GSI Geneva	Extracting information from electromagnetic monitors in Hadron Accelerators	32	3	4
4	25-27 June 2018	DESY & PSI Hamburg	Longitudinal Diagnostics at FELs (co-sponsoring)	45	5	-
5 & 6	12-14 Nov. 2018	ALBA & GSI Barcelona	Next Generation Beam Position Acquisition and Feedback Systems Two in one event: hadron & electron acc.	84	3 & 4	-
7	1-3 April 2019	GSI & SOLARIS Krakow	Scintillation Screens and Optical Technology for transverse Profile Measurements	49	2	4 & 5
8	3-5 June 2019	ALBA & ESRF Grenoble	Diagnostics Experts of European Light Sources (DEELS 19) (co-sponsoring)	33	4	
9	25-29 Jan. 2021	CIEMAT & GSI Online	Experiences during Hadron LINAC Commissioning	239	2	
10	21-23 June 2021	CERN & GSI Online	Materials and Engineering for Particle Accelerator Beam Diagnostic Instruments	205	3	2, 4 & 5
11	7-8 July 2021	ALBA & SESAME Online	Diagnostics Experts of European Light Sources (DEELS 21) (co-sponsoring)	49	4	

Table 1 summarises the subjects of the workshops, including some basic numbers, such as the duration, the number of delegates, link to the workshop INDICO-site and the involved ARIES-ADA tasks. Several of the workshops were summarised at the beam instrumentation conference IBIC series for a larger audience, showing the relevance of the discussed projects and the importance of the funding by the European Community; clear credits are given to the EU funding. The related papers are:

- Invited talk at IBIC 2018 by Ubaldo Iriso: “Summary of Emittance Measurements Workshop for SLS and FELs”; no proceedings were written.
- Poster contribution at IBIC 2018 by Peter Forck: “ARIES-ADA: An R&D Network for Advanced Diagnostics at Accelerators”; related conference proceeding Ref. [1].

- Invited talk at IBIC 2019 by Beata Walasek-Höhne: “Screens for High Precision Measurements”; related conference proceeding Ref. [2].
- Invited talk at IBIC 2019 by Guenther Rehm: "Characterization of Closed Orbit Feedback Systems”; related conference proceeding Ref. [3].
- Contributed talk at IBIC 2021 by Peter Forck: “Summary of the ARIES Workshop on Materials and Engineering Technologies for Particle Accelerator Beam Diagnostic Instruments”; related conference proceeding Ref. [4].

Most of the ARIES-ADA budget was used to cover the event costs such as venue rent, the cost for coffee breaks and refreshments and administrative issues. Some parts of the travel costs for delegates were covered; this enabled the participation of young scientists and people from institutes with a low amount of travel budget, increasing the intentionality of the events.

In addition to the workshops, the ARIES-ADA budget was used to finance the personnel exchanges for three scientists and duration between two and four weeks. In all cases, a relation to one of the workshop subjects exists. In particular, early-stage scientists benefitted significantly. The involved institutions were:

- A scientist from Fermilab (USA) visited GSI related to Ionization Profile Monitor development
- A scientist from the University of Milan visited ALBA related to high-resolution profile measurement at light sources
- A scientist from GSI visited Diamond Light Source related to the closed orbit feedback design at synchrotrons; this scientific discussion contributed to peer-reviewed journal articles Ref. [5, 6].

Several further visits were scheduled but could not be realized due to the travel restrictions that showed up at the end of 2019. It concerned visits of a Chinese scientist from IMP at GSI, a Jordanian scientist from SESAME at ALBA, two German scientists from GSI to the Brazilian light source SIRIUS.

Generally, the COVID-19 pandemic had a significant impact on the exchange of personnel, resulting in the complete cancellation of visits from the beginning of the year 2020. Workshops were foreseen as in-person events to enable a familiar atmosphere with senior people who met young scientist engineers to force discussions about layout details and 'tricks', which are usually not discussed at large conferences and were very helpful for successfully designing and operating beam instrumentation. Therefore, the planned workshops were postponed, hoping for in-person meetings in autumn 2020 to spring 2021. As it turned out that this was impossible, online workshops were organized. This format had the advantage that significantly more delegates participated, particularly from China, Japan, and Korea. In this sense, the scope was even widened, and the project ARIES is now well-known in the worldwide instrumentation community. However, a delay for ARIES-ADA was caused by the change of the workshop format and the related scope modification. Further workshops were initially planned but could not be realized in the remaining time frame.

To conclude: Thanks to the funding by the EU, the project ARIES-ADA organized special topic workshops covering actual subjects of great importance, strengthened the collaboration due to the workshops and the exchange of personnel, and were very positively recognized by the beam instrumentation community.

In the main text, the individual workshops are briefly summarised. A detailed workshop summary is attached for each workshop. It serves as an introduction to the individual contributions and is also published on the corresponding workshop INDICO-site. As different authors wrote the text, the style and length varied.

2. Task 1 on Work-package Coordination

The task leaders jointly executed the work-package coordination. Several informal meetings took place at conferences or other meetings of the related persons. For each workshop, dedicated teams were built together with the experts on the topic. Several non-beneficiary institutes contributed significantly, such as CIEMAT, ELETTRA, ESRF, FNAL, J-PARC, KEK, PSI, SOLARIS, SOLEIL, SNS, TRIUMF; in this sense, the work-package transformed into a successful international activity.

3. Progress in Beam Diagnostics for Hadron LINACs (Task 2)

3.1 WORKSHOP ON 'SIMULATION, DESIGN & OPERATION OF IONIZATION PROFILE MONITORS'

In May 2017, a Topical Workshop at GSI concerning '[Simulation, Design & Operation of Ionization Profile Monitors](http://indico.gsi.de/event/5366/)' (<http://indico.gsi.de/event/5366/>) with 33 participants from Europe, North America and Asia. It was organized as a joint event of Task 8.2 (hadron LINACs) and 8.3 (hadron synchrotrons). An Ionization Profile Monitor (IPM) is based on spatially resolving the ions or electrons generated from residual gas ionization via beam impact. These monitors deliver the beam profile in a non-destructive manner with a spatial resolution of typically 50 μm and time gating down to the 10 ns level. They are installed at both hadron LINACs and synchrotrons. Due to the increase in the beam power of future LINACs (e.g. at CERN, ESS, FAIR, ISIS) these IPMs will substitute the traditional invasive wire-based diagnostics. Even though the principle is well known, there are many technical challenges for such beam instrumentation's stable and reliable operation. The experts in the field presented the experience and technical solutions from installations worldwide. The results were extensively discussed, and the related contributions serve as a comprehensive catalogue of such systems.

The workshop's primary purpose was to introduce the community to a recently completed simulation code called IPMSim, <https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/IPMSim/>. This code was produced with the input of several experts to simulate the related physical processes (cross-section for electron and ion production) under various conditions (beam distribution, space charge, external field configurations) from non-relativistic beams at LINACs to highly energetic beams at synchrotrons. The code features a modern programming style, a user-friendly GUI and can easily be expanded to include new physical models and applications. The code is freely available, and its benchmarking was successfully demonstrated. Further extensions of the code (e.g. for Beam Induced Fluorescence Monitors) are now realized. Possible experimental verifications of such simulations were put forward at this workshop, and several have now been performed.

As foreseen in the ARIES proposal, an exchange of personnel was made possible, with Dr. J. Zagel from Fermilab (USA) staying at GSI for several weeks to discuss IPM related topics and possible improvements to these systems at GSI.

3.2 WORKSHOP ON 'SCINTILLATION SCREENS AND OPTICAL TECHNOLOGY FOR TRANSVERSE PROFILE MEASUREMENTS'

The Topical Workshop '[Scintillation Screens and Optical Technology for transverse Profile Measurements](https://indico.cern.ch/event/765975/)' (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/765975/>) took place in April 2019 in Krakow, Poland with 49 participants organized by GSI in collaboration with the Polish Light Source SOLARIS. It was a joint event of all tasks as scintillation screens are installed at almost every type of accelerator, including laser-plasma accelerators. Industrial partners contributed with three scientific talks. The

workshop included an industrial exhibition with four booths. A guided tour at SOLARIS took place on the third day.

The first topic of the workshop was related to the understanding of the scintillation process. Experts in inorganic scintillation research presented two overview talks discussing scintillator physics and recent technological developments. The regular application of scintillators at high energy physics, medical imaging or homeland security is focused on high sensitivity with a low count rate. In contrast to the application in beam instrumentation, the screen is directly irradiated by the primary beam, which might have a high flux within short bunches (e.g. at FEL facilities) or with high energy deposition (e.g. at ion facilities). Several scintillation materials were investigated for various beam parameters, and the results from several facilities were presented.

To achieve the required resolution for the profile measurements, dedicated optics has to be installed in the vicinity of the beam pipe. Detailed optical realizations were presented depicting solutions for these unusual geometries (e.g. Scheimpflug orientation). The advanced technical realizations at 3rd and 4th generation light sources were shown, and related experiences were discussed, including the suppression of coherent optical transition radiation.

The existing camera technologies were summarised by an industrial producer of high-performance cameras showing the pro and cons of the various sensor types. Radiation hardness tests of cameras were performed at CHARM@CERN, showing the requirements for novel cameras that survive the typical radiation levels at hadron facilities. Additionally, the usage of optical fibres was discussed.

A large fraction of the contributions discussed the properties of the different scintillators for hadron and electron beams. Experimental and theoretical investigations were presented concerning radiation damage by hadron beams, e.g. relevant for the target diagnostics at SNS and ESS. For intense electron beams, e.g. at DESY XFEL saturations effect were observed, and an explanation model was developed. The technical realization and the experiences at various facilities were discussed.

3.3 WORKSHOP ON 'EXPERIENCES DURING HADRON LINAC COMMISSIONING.'

The Topical Workshop '[Experiences during Hadron LINAC Commissioning](https://agenda.ciemat.es/event/1229/)' (<https://agenda.ciemat.es/event/1229/>) took place in January 2021 as a remote event jointly organized by CIEMAT and GSI comprising of five half-day sessions. 239 delegates registered, and about 100 people were simultaneously connected; see graphic in the detailed summary part. The interest by the community, as measured by the number of delegates, was significantly larger than anticipated. Initially, the workshop was planned for June 2020 as an in-person event.

Several proton and ion LINACs were commissioned in the past years, such as LINAC4, PIP-II, SARAF, Spiral2, or are in the commissioning phase, such as ESS FRIB, HELIAC, LIPAc. Even at existing LINACs, such as BNL, GSI, J-PARC, SNS, significant developments are ongoing, and reports on the related experiences are of mutual interest. The aims of this workshop were:

- Bring together instrument designers, experts, and research groups working on proton or ion linear accelerators' commissioning.
- Review the experiences on the commissioning of hadron LINACs from the first day of operation to more regular operation.

- Discuss the discrepancies between the beam instruments requirements specified at the design phase and the real needs and applications requirements during commissioning.
- Explore the feedback about the LINAC layout and usage of diagnostics test benches during stage-based commissioning.

Most of the contributions were given by experts responsible for the commissioning and operation of the LINACs. The speakers described the requirements formulated for the day-one operation to the time of regular operation and detailed accelerator physics investigations.

The experiences during step-wise commissioning (enabling detailed accelerator-physics investigations) were described and weighted to the quicker installation phase by installing a significant part of the LINAC in one step. For both attempts, the methodology was supported with various examples. These were essential statements for the beam diagnostics community for an appropriate instrumentation layout.

The use of various beam instrumentation was discussed with its data acquisition systems and graphical user interfaces. The potential for automatic beam alignment was investigated at several facilities using different methods, ranging from traditional deterministic algorithms to machine learning applications as a trendsetting topic. The realization and usage caused some controversial discussions.

On the fifth day, several speakers presented special instruments, which have, or will have, applications for operation and accelerator-physics investigations. Further speakers discussed the perspective of industry producing beam instrumentation or a significant part of a LINAC facility.

3.4 CONCLUSION FOR HADRON LINAC BEAM DIAGNOSTICS

The objective of the initial proposal aims for the reduction of losses and a safe operation of high power LINACs. This goal is reached, as several relevant topics related to non-invasive measurement techniques were discussed and are now improved. In particular, this concerns the non-invasive transverse profile measurement technology (discussed at the workshop section 3.1), applications for phase measurement (discussed at the third workshop, section 3.3), and automated beam manipulation techniques including machine learning algorithms (partly covered at the workshop section 3.3).

Non-invasive profile measurements are non-standard methods at high current LINACs but are required to allow for the observation of the entire macro-pulse; contrary to SEM-Grids or wire scanners that require a shortening of the macro-pulse to prevent for overheating. One subject of the topic workshop (section 3.1) was the technical realizations for IPMs at different facilities and information about construction details. As the main topic, the simulation code IPMSim were introduced to the community. In the time between the workshop (May 2017) and the drafting of the report (mid-2021), the code is significantly enhanced and now used at different labs. The code also includes the simulation of further non-invasive profile measurements such as Beam Induced Fluorescence. Moreover, it can serve as a basis for supervised machine learning correction algorithms required for very intense beams at hadron LINACs and synchrotrons.

At the second workshop (section 3.2), applications for all types of accelerators related to scintillation screens were discussed. The general understanding of the process and its applicability was the workshop's main topic. Screens are applied regularly for profile measurements for hadron LINACs of low and medium intensities. The achievable light yield and possible radiation damage are of importance, and the workshop contributed to the understanding of the related physical processes enabling an appropriate choice of the scintillation material. For high current LINACs, pepper-pot emittance relay on the usage of screens, and innovative proposals were discussed. In addition, the applicability of scintillation screens for laser-accelerated beams were presented. Innovative camera technology for low light detection was an additional topic. Radiation hardness differs for several scintillator materials, and an appropriate choice is of great relevance at high power hadron LINACs.

The third workshop (section 3.3) concerned the central topic for beam instrumentation and their usage during the LINAC commissioning, and first stages of operation. People from instrumentation, operation and beam dynamics contributed in a balanced manner. It is interesting to note that phase measurements are vital to achieve the matching between the accelerating cavities and serve as one of the essential alignment tools. Automatic cavity amplitude and phase alignment methods were successfully applied at several facilities. First trials concerning automatic beam steering based on machine learning were discussed, proving the applicability of modern techniques. The improvement of those technologies is one of the objectives of ARIES-ADA. In general, the comparison of achievements at various facilities serves as a solid basis for future LINACs and their commissioning.

The workshop on mechanical issues (summarized below in section 4.3) contained many aspects relevant for hadron LINACs. This concerns, e.g. the production of SEM-Grid and wire scanners using Carbon Nano Tubes. Moreover, adaptive manufacturing is demonstrated with these instruments leading to an optimized production method; the vacuum requirements can be fulfilled. Novel methods for blackening of vacuum chambers are of great relevance for the non-invasive profile measurement method by Beam Induced Fluorescence. This photon detection method is an alternative to IPMs and brought into operation at several LINACs in the last years. Magnetically controlled vacuum drives are an excellent alternative to bellow-based drives due to their enhanced lifetime.

4. Advances in Beam Diagnostics for Hadron Synchrotrons (Task 3)

4.1 WORKSHOP ON 'EXTRACTING INFORMATION FROM ELECTROMAGNETIC MONITORS IN HADRON ACCELERATORS'

A topical workshop with 32 participants on ['Extracting Information from electromagnetic monitors in Hadron Accelerators'](https://indico.cern.ch/event/705430/) (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/705430/>) took place in May 2018 at CERN. The goal was to strengthen the collaboration between the beam dynamics and beam instrumentation community as both communities have to contribute to a correct interpretation of advanced beam measurement methods. Additionally, people working at circular light sources participated as the topic is equally essential for the electron- and hadron synchrotrons.

The workshop focused on various measurement methods of lattice parameters at synchrotrons, such as the machine tune and chromaticity. Recent results concerning betatron-function measurement and beta-beating determination were discussed. The different methods used for optics measurements were summarised in an overview talk. It was shown that part of the progress is related to improvements in the BPM readout's achievable accuracy. The applicability of methods leading to significant noise reduction of the BPM data was demonstrated in several contributions. Moreover, the determination of advanced parameters such as intensity-dependent tune shift and tune spread determined via quadrupolar oscillations is a hot topic and intensively discussed between instrumentation and beam dynamics experts. A comparison between simulations and measurements at CERN PS shows a good correspondence, as had been depicted in one of the contributions.

Further on, Schottky signal analysis was discussed in several contributions. This method enables the observation of many parameters such as momentum spread, tune, chromaticity without any influence on the beam. The applicability for coasting and bunched beams for daily operation and detailed machine studies were discussed. The advanced Schottky system at LHC was recently commissioned and enabled online determination, e.g. of tune and chromaticity. Using Schottky analysis, it is possible to perform BPM-based position measurements for coasting beams. The collection of all those contributions serve as a comprehensive collection of the standard and advanced applications.

4.2 WORKSHOP ON 'NEXT GENERATION BEAM POSITION ACQUISITION AND FEEDBACK SYSTEMS'

The Topical Workshop on ['Next Generation Beam Position Acquisition and Feedback Systems'](https://indico.cern.ch/event/743699/) (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/743699/>) was organized as a joint event between task 8.3 (hadron synchrotron) and 8.4 (circular light sources). It took place in Barcelona in November 2018 with 84 participants. The first day was related to the analogue and digital electronics for BPMs at hadron synchrotrons, the second day as a joint event related to the closed orbit feedback systems and the third day with the subject of bunch-by-bunch feedback system at light sources to cure instabilities. Industrial partners contributed with two scientific talks.

The design considerations of analogue and digital electronics for the BPMs at hadron synchrotrons were presented on the first day. In particular, the methods to achieve the required resolution and

accuracy were discussed. Here the injection of a 'pilot tone' seems to be an excellent method; it is based on the injection of a signal beside the acceleration frequency band followed by appropriate filtering to distinguish between the injected signal and the beam signal. Further realizations of analogue electronics were discussed. An alternative to commercial products was shown for digital electronics based on 'open hardware repository' www.ohwr.org (hardware solutions can be copied under a GNU-type licence); GSI and Brazilian Light Source reported on positive experiences.

The closed orbit feedback system at electron and hadron synchrotrons was compared on the second day. Many familiar aspects exist, even though the applications seem to be different: At electron synchrotrons, mainly mechanical vibrations lead to closed orbit distortions, while hysteresis effects are more critical at hadron booster rings. An increase of the feedback bandwidth is envisaged for the next-generation light sources to improve the damping rate significantly. Presently, the latency for the feedback system is mainly given by the bandwidth of the corrector power suppliers; a contribution from PSI summarised their power supplier developments. Further on, the controller types and the mathematical basis for the inversion of the orbit response matrix were discussed, and the applicability of novel feedback algorithms was reported based on general symmetry considerations on Discrete Fourier Transformation, which have some advantages over the traditional Singular Value Decomposition.

The third day was devoted to the fast, bunch-by-bunch feedback system. A general overview was given in a talk by an industrial partner. The different realizations at the various facilities were discussed using either commercial hardware or unique homemade designs. The feedback system can also be used to monitor the beam's growth rates for detailed machine studies.

A related exchange of personnel took place in June 2018 by the GSI employee Sajjad Hussain Mirza to work for two weeks at the UK Diamond Light Source on topics related to closed orbit feedback. The collaboration led to a peer-reviewed journal article [5].

4.3 WORKSHOP ON 'MATERIALS AND ENGINEERING FOR PARTICLE ACCELERATOR BEAM DIAGNOSTIC INSTRUMENTS'

The Topical Workshop '[Materials and Engineering for Particle Accelerator Beam Diagnostic Instruments](https://indico.cern.ch/event/863675/)' (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/863675/>) was organized by CERN and GSI in connection the Department of Engineering Science of University-Oxford and concerned all ARIES-ADA tasks. It took place as a remote event in June 2021 for three half-days. 205 delegates were registered, and about 100 people participated simultaneously, see graphic in the detailed workshop summary.

As a novelty for these workshops, the speakers of the individual sessions were asked to enter separate breakout rooms to enable a discussion with interested workshop participants. As the workshop's topics are not very frequently presented at conferences, the individual private discussions were intensively used to clarify details and enable personal contacts. This procedure was very well accepted, and intense discussions on dedicated topics were executed.

Initially, the workshop was planned as an in-person meeting in Oxford end of March 2020 with 50 participants and 32 talks. However, it was cancelled only two weeks in advance due to the pandemic's start in Europe.

The workshop was targeted to the design and technology of physical instruments, which receives relatively little coverage in conferences and existing scientific literature. This finding might be caused by the fact that engineers rarely participate in regular conferences; however, most contributions were given by the engineers working on the beam instrument design in this workshop. The focus was on advanced mechanical concepts, design and technologies for realizations. The discussed topics were related to:

- Novel materials and production, e.g. ultra-thin wires for wire scanners and SEM-Grid
- Novel materials for vacuum installations with improved properties
- Precise vacuum installations and drives, e.g. magnetically coupled
- Improved methods for mechanical development & production, e.g. 3-d printing
- Review the state-of-the-art materials & production technologies.

The first topic of the workshops concerned wire scanners and SEM-Grids. Even though this seems to be an old technology, the challenge for linear light sources is the production of thin wires in the order of only 1 μm , which was realized for SwissFEL and FERMI and successfully tested. With this technology, beam sizes down to 0.5 μm can be resolved. For the fast wire scanner, as, e.g. used at CERN synchrotrons, the stability of the wire is an issue due to the enormous acceleration to a velocity of 20 m/s and the thermal resilience related to the immense beam power. The usage of novel Carbon Nano Tubes is a solution investigated with several methods at CERN and University-Oxford. The design of the motor, vacuum components and position reading have to use novel techniques as well.

Adaptive manufacturing by 3D printing of the fast scanner's wire fork was demonstrated as a mechanically complex device; the forks are now in regular operation. The vacuum compatibility of the 3D printed devices was demonstrated. Practical experiences for the 3d printing process were discussed in a separate talk, showing the applicability of this method for several further examples. The production method of SEM-Grid at CERN was discussed to produce an equally stressed wire array. Moreover, good experiences were reported for in-vacuum usage of so-called flex PCBs for the insulated connection between the SEM-Grid and the vacuum flange.

Two further applications of Nano Tubes were introduced at the workshop. The first application concerns the blackening of vacuum components; as reported by the company Vantablack, reflections below 0.1 % can be achieved. Secondly, a scintillator can be produced from boron-nitride for transverse profile measurements; functional tests with electron and ion beams were executed, proving the superior functionality.

The manufacturer described a novel generation of vacuum drives using magnetical coupling. The achievements are related to low magnetic stray fields, achievable precision of the movement, and ultra-high vacuum compatibility using novel grease-free metal rolling bearing. Detailed outgassing measurements of polymers were discussed, giving a good overview of the usability of insulators for in-vacuum installations. New sealing technologies for large vacuum flanges were successfully tested at DESY. Moreover, the proposed substitution of the regular stainless steel 316NL by 'Alloy 50' is used for ultra-high vacuum applications.

4.4 CONCLUSION FOR HADRON SYNCHROTRON BEAM DIAGNOSTICS

The objective of this task was to establish methods for precise position measurement and orbit feedback, as well as the determination of lattice functions. Both topics were extensively covered by the workshops described in sections 4.1 and 4.2.

The first topic workshop (section 4.1) brought together beam dynamics and instrumentation experts to discuss the information required and achievable to increase the understanding and operational usage of electromagnetic monitors. Innovative numerical analysis methods can significantly improve an existing BPM system's capability. Modification of the recorded BPM frequency spectrum can be related to beam intensity effects. In particular, if dipole or quadrupole Beam Transfer Functions are executed, a theory-based interpretation is required to model related effects. Schottky signal analysis delivers rich information on the momentum distribution, transverse and longitudinal tunes, and chromaticity. As for the BTF, intensity effects modify the frequency spectrum, and the workshop contributed significantly to knowledge transfer between the beam dynamics and instrumentation community.

The objective of precise beam position measurement was one of the topics of the second workshop (section 4.2). Gain stability of the analogue electronics is a complex design challenge to achieve the required position accuracy, and experiences on the engineering level were discussed in detail. In particular, the 'pilot tone' injection method is now implemented at several hadron and electron synchrotrons to improve position accuracy. The exchange of experiences for both accelerator types can significantly improve the realization of next-generation electronics. The 'open hardware repository' can serve as a basis for efficient electronics production. Advanced digital evaluation methods can improve the resolution and the robustness against electromagnetic interference. The topic of closed orbit feedback is comparable for hadron and electron synchrotrons, even though the source of disturbance might be different. The advantages of novel correction algorithms based on general principles (DFT versus SVD decomposition, see Ref. [5]) were described and adapted for the application at different synchrotrons.

The workshop on material and engineering (section 4.3) was organized by this task to discuss modern trends in mechanical engineering, which concerns all types of accelerators. For the synchrotron applications, adaptive manufacturing is of excellent innovation potential as complex structures can be produced; it was shown that the vacuum requirements could be fulfilled. Secondly, Nano Tube material has its applications for wire scanners due to low weight and high mechanical stability; both technologies were applied for the CERN synchrotrons. Such blackening with Nano Tubes was recently installed in the LHC for Beam Induced Fluorescence profile measurements. Further meaningful experiences were reported at this workshop and will support the engineering design of beam instrumentation.

The third objective of this task, namely non-invasive profile measurements, was discussed in the workshop on IPMs (described above in section 3.1). For the transverse profile measurements in synchrotrons, a significant measured profile deformation might occur for intense beams. The code IPMSim can simulate this effect and is recently used for machine learning-based corrections as introduced during the workshop. Supervised learning via Neuronal Network related to image

recognition serves as an innovative method and progresses significantly in the meantime from the workshop to the drafting of this report (May 2017 to 2021).

5. Advances in Beam Diagnostics for 3rd Generation Light Sources (Task 4)

5.1 WORKSHOP ON 'NEXT GENERATION BEAM POSITION ACQUISITION AND FEEDBACK SYSTEMS'

The Topical Workshop on '[Next Generation Beam Position Acquisition and Feedback Systems](https://indico.cern.ch/event/743699/)' (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/743699/>) was organized as a joint event between task 8.3 (hadron synchrotron) and task 8.4 (circular light sources) and is summarized above in section 4.2.

5.2 WORKSHOP ON 'DIAGNOSTICS EXPERTS OF EUROPEAN LIGHT SOURCES (DEELS 19)'

The Topical Workshop [Diagnostics Experts of European Light Sources \(DEELS19\)](https://indico.cern.ch/event/789811/) (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/789811/>) took place in June 2019 in Grenoble with 33 participants jointly organized by ESRF and ALBA. It is based on a series of yearly meetings established six years ago. Thanks to the funding by ARIES, colleagues from Asia and America could participate.

As the main workshop topic, multiple projects of new electronics developments for Beam Position Monitors (BPM) were presented. Those new developments are motivated by two reasons: Firstly, the recent progress in FPGA chips open new possibilities and, secondly, stringent requirements for orbit feedback at ultra-low emittance synchrotrons. A BPM platform currently developed by ELETTRA focuses on modularity; it uses the 'pilot-tone' scheme to calibrate the analogue front-end and cable transmission drifts. High performances FGPA and Analog to Digital Converters are used at other facilities to achieve bunch-by-bunch measurements.

Concerning BPM measurement resolution and accuracy, some presentations focused on sources of error, together with proposed solutions to increase BPM performances and mitigate imprecise settings. This concerns online rf-measurements (like 'pilot-tone' injection) and statistical methods to enable a software-based online correction. Moreover, the effect of temperature and humidity on RF cables' transmission was investigated extensively.

As a further topic, ALBA presented a versatile software tool called "BPMLab" to compute the position resolution of a BPM; ESRF presented the software OASYS for synchrotron radiation simulations. Other topics were related to spatially resolved beam loss measurements using a scintillating fibre with modern light detectors (SiPM) at ALBA. Further BLM systems were described. Overview talks covered recent development for longitudinal diagnostics at SPRING8 and a THz diagnostics beamline design.

5.3 WORKSHOP ON 'DIAGNOSTICS EXPERTS OF EUROPEAN LIGHT SOURCES (DEELS 21)'

The Topical Workshop '[Diagnostics Experts of European Light Sources \(DEELS 21\)](https://indico.cern.ch/event/1027295/)' (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/1027295/>) of task 8.4 (circular light sources) took place in July 2021 as

a remote event jointly organized by ALBA and SESAME as a one plus half-day event. It was the first time the mid-east facility hosted such a workshop of this type. 49 participants from 20 institutions were registered, among them delegates from universities in Egypt and Pakistan and 2 industrial companies.

One topic was the SESAME facility and its beam instrumentation which was not discussed in such detail at previous workshops. The audience was impressed by the progress made for this light source and the use of solar panels to supply the required energy for this machine. This is a clear example of green energy in the accelerator environment. In addition, the workshop included a virtual guided tour at this facility.

A second focus of the workshop was related to photon diagnostics. It comprised the design and usage of X-ray BPMs, which are nowadays foreseen as part of the closed orbit stabilization system. For the novel ultra-low emittance storage rings, such devices will serve as the primary monitors to fulfil the extreme demands on beam stability. The technical realization at Diamond, SESAME and SOLEIL was presented.

Other topics were related to techniques for bunch length recording using visible light, as realized at ESRF, and is now in operation. An innovative image reconstruction method by an Artificial Neural Network was realized for the transverse profile measurement at ALBA. The related method caused an intensive discussion.

5.4 CONCLUSION FOR ELECTRON SYNCHROTRON BEAM DIAGNOSTICS

The first objective of this task, namely the implementation of a performant orbit feedback, was discussed together with the experts from hadron synchrotrons (section 4.2). Combining the experiences from hadron and electron synchrotron applications, an overview of the state-of-the-art realizations could be achieved, and novel digital correction algorithms were successfully applied, see above in section 4.4. At this workshop, the properties of bunch-by-bunch feedback systems to cure beam instabilities were discussed, and their realizations at several light sources were presented. A commercial solution is available, designed by a leading scientist in the field. Improvements of the ultra-low emittance light sources are required, and the network of experts can contribute to the realization of the various projects. The contribution by engineers assigned to the realization of fast signal processing was a major achievement of the workshop.

Even though, the DEELS workshops were established prior to the start of ARIES-ADA, the co-sponsoring contributes to an enlargement of participants from Asia and America. This led to additional delegates and contributions to the topic (section 5.2 and 5.3). It is a success that SESAME (Jordan) contribute now to the workshop (due to the COVID-19 crisis, the planned in-person workshop could not be realized). Accurate position reading is a major beam diagnostic and will get even more challenging for the ultra-low emittance rings. State-of-the-art technical realizations were discussed at both meetings in detail. 'Pilot tone' injection can improve the accuracy of the analogue signal chain, and FPGA-based position calculation codes are shared between the institutes. The inclusion of X-ray BPMs (detecting the photon beam) into the closed orbit feedback is foreseen for several light source upgrades and is a new challenge, and a network can collect ideas leading to first technical designs.

The objective of innovative transverse profile measurement methods was intensively discussed at the workshop summarized in section 6.1 below. For the ultra-low emittance rings, the beam size is only several μm , and the traditional methods are insufficient. Significant improvements of the existing methods are urgently required to achieve the required resolution, or novel technologies must be applied. Various attempts were discussed during the workshop, and a compilation of the present status are summarized in Table 2; more details are described in the attached detailed workshop summary. This table serves as a reference for any future development. The discussion on the best-suited method is still ongoing and await the practical demonstration at several facilities.

Table 2: Comparison of profile measurement methods at circular light sources using synchrotron light monitors in the visible or X-ray range: The used technology and the achieved spatial resolution are given together with the presenter's name of the workshop contribution.

Method for <u>circular</u> accelerator	smallest σ [μm] (measured)	Workshop Presenter
Scintillator (reference)	1.5	G. Kube (DESY)
X-ray Pinhole	7	L. Bobb (DLS)/ F. Ewald (ESRF)
Comp. Refractive Lenses	10	F. Ewald (ESRF)/ A. Snigirev (Kalin.)
Vis. Light Interf.	3.9	T. Mitsunashi (KEK)
Vis. Light Inter. (mask)	2 (sim)	L. Torino (ESRF)
p-polarization (vis)	3.7	A. Andersson (MAXLab)
Coded Aperture	5	J. Flanagan (KEK)
In-air X-ray Det.	9	F. Ewald (ESRF)
X-ray Diffraction	4.8	A. Snigirev (Kaliningrad)
X-ray (multi/lens) Inter.	4.8	A. Snigirev (Kaliningrad)
HNFS	130	M. Siano (Milan)

6. Advances in Beam Diagnostics for Free Electron Lasers and Electron LINACs (Task5)

6.1 WORKSHOP ON 'EMITTANCE MEASUREMENTS FOR LIGHT SOURCES AND FELs'

The Topical Workshop '[Emittance Measurements for Light Sources and FELs](https://indico.cells.es/indico/event/128/)' (<https://indico.cells.es/indico/event/128/>) was held at ALBA in January 2018, organized by Task 8.4 (circular light sources) with the collaboration of Task 8.5 (linear light sources). The workshop addressed challenges for the next generation of ultra-low emittance machines and LINAC-based FELs. One day was devoted to emittance measurements at synchrotron light sources and the second day at Free Electron Lasers. Experts working on emittance measurements for other types of machines, such as hadron synchrotrons and Laser Plasma Accelerators were also invited to discuss possible synergies between the different communities.

For synchrotron light sources, the review of present techniques using synchrotron radiation showed that beam sizes down to the 2-3 μm level could be measured through the careful design and choice of instrumentation. These techniques include direct imaging techniques (X-ray pinhole cameras, Compound Refractive Lenses, or in-air X-ray detectors) and techniques based on the analysis of light coherence (visible light interferometers). Since this is at the limit for the beam sizes foreseen for the next generation of low emittance rings, the benefits of more complex techniques such as X-ray diffraction/interferometry and Heterodyne Speckle Fields (HNFS) were also profoundly discussed during the workshop. The workshop concluded that these techniques would need specific beamlines foreseen for their operation.

For Free Electron Lasers, beam sizes are typically measured using invasive methods through the beam's interaction with movable obstacles, such as Optical Transition Radiation screens or wire scanners. It was shown that wires as thin as 1 μm can now be manufactured using lithographic techniques, which allows the measurement of beam sizes down to 500 nm. In addition, the current status of techniques such as laser wire measurements or Optical Diffraction Radiation Interferometry, the workshop also addressed new, innovative techniques such as those using Cherenkov Diffraction Radiation.

An exchange of personnel was organized within the frame of this workshop, with M. Siano (Univ. Milano) staying at ALBA to discuss the HNFS technique and to perform tests in an ALBA beamline.

6.2 WORKSHOP ON 'LONGITUDINAL DIAGNOSTICS AT FREE ELECTRON LASERS'

The Topical Workshop '[Longitudinal Diagnostics for Free-Electron Lasers](https://indico.cern.ch/event/702602/)', (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/702602/>) took place in June 2018 at DESY with 45 participants. The workshop aimed to foster joint developments of longitudinal diagnostics for femtosecond electron bunches and bring together experts working on beam instrumentation and detector development. Several participants working in the field of Laser Plasma Accelerators contributed to the workshop as these novel short-bunch accelerators face even higher demands concerning the time resolution. The topic of transverse deflecting structures (TDS) was intentionally excluded as there is a strong collaboration between CERN, PSI, and DESY on developing an X-Band TDS with regular meetings.

The workshop was organized in 5 working groups to exchange ideas, plan collaborations or measurement campaigns. The first day of the workshop was devoted to discussions within these working groups. On the second and third days, the working group coordinators reported the discussion results, and the participants presented their contributions in poster sessions.

Compression Monitors and THz Detectors: The intense coherent THz and IR part of diffraction or edge radiation emitted by the electron bunches is commonly used as a compression monitor for feedback on the accelerator phase. The THz/IR beam transport, attenuation and detection need to be optimized depending on the bunch charge, profile and repetition rate. Further improvements of a multi-array Schottky diode detector developed by TU Dresden as a THz spectrometer were identified.

Electro-Optical Diagnostics: Electro-optical techniques are limited in time resolution but are entirely non-invasive. Different readout schemes were discussed to achieve single-bunch resolution at MHz repetition rates. Joint experiments were planned.

THz Streak of the primary electron beam: The goal of this working group was to discuss possibilities to streak the electron beam in a micro-structure operating at THz frequencies. The aim is to improve the resolution of radio frequency deflectors by increasing both frequency and deflecting fields. The application to low-energy beams has been presented, and further studies at high-energy facilities were planned.

KALYPSO and fast digitization: The KALYPSO (Kalruhe Linear detector for MHz-rePetition rate Spectroscopy) linear detector system has been developed as a flexible digitizer board to be compatible with different front-end electronic standards for many applications. Requirements for the next improved version were defined by the various applications of the linear detector board.

Laser Heater operation and diagnostics: The aim was to share the experience of laser heater operation and optimization for the suppression of micro-bunching instabilities gained at different facilities. The cathode material of the photo-injector, e.g. Cu or Ce₂Te, seems to influence the micro-bunching instabilities and, in addition to that, on the operation of the laser heater. Further joint studies were discussed.

6.3 CONCLUSION FOR ELECTRON LINAC BEAM DIAGNOSTICS

Transverse profile measurements are a major tool for beam alignment and accelerator development for the linear light sources. Intersecting methods are frequently used but must be designed with great care. One topic is the suppression of coherent optical transition. More complex photon-detection methods were discussed, like diffraction radiation interferometry or the usage of Cherenkov radiation. These methods are pretty complex, and technical realizations are presently ongoing; design ideas were interchanged during the workshop (section 6.1). Another route is the usage of wire scanners with ultra-thin wires produced by lithographic processes. Laser wire scanners based on the inverse Compton effect act as an alternative; however, they are not technically a standard operational tool. One major outcome of the workshop was a comparison of resolution achievement for the various methods depicted in table 3; more details are discussed in the attached workshop summary. The production details of thin wire scanners were one major part of the workshop on material and engineering (section 4.3), where beam-based measurements demonstrated the technical realization.

Table 3: Comparison of different methods at linear light sources. The used technology and the achieved spatial resolution is given together with the presenter's name of the workshop contribution.

Method for <u>linear</u> accelerator	smallest σ [μm] (measured)	Workshop Presenter
Scintillator (reference)	1.5	G. Kube (DESY)
OTR Techniques	1.5	L. Sukhikh (Tomsk)
ODRI Techniques	??	E. Chiadroni (INFN)
COTR Techniques	3.8	A. Potylitsyn (Tomsk)
Wire Scanner Technique	0.490	K. Wittenburg (DESY) / S. Borrelli (PSI)
Laser Wire Technique	0.070	P. Karataev (RHUL)
Multi-Slit Mask Technique	200	M. Kraskilnikov (DESY)

Transverse profile measurements for linear light sources motivated the workshop on scintillation screens (section 3.2) to overcome the image deformation by coherent optical transition radiation. Hence, scintillating screens are presently used at FEL facilities. A given material's scintillation properties play a significant role in preventing, e.g. for saturation effects. Discussion between instrumentation specialists and manufacturers' representatives led to more appropriate customized design considerations. To achieve the required spatial resolution in the order of 1 μm , dedicated optical systems must be installed; the recent realization at DESY and PSI serves as a reference.

The central objective of bunch length measurement was covered by one workshop (section 6.2). It was a lengthy workshop with world-leading delegates and detailed working group discussions. In addition, the workshop included poster sessions. Major technologies were presented: Electro-optical methods and THz serve as complementary methods; the general layouts and technical realizations were discussed in detail. Experiences with laser-heaters for the instability suppressing widened the spectrum of activities with this workshop. The workshop serves as a comprehensive summary concerning the state-of-the-art diagnostics method for bunch length measurements.

Another objective, namely the high precision position monitoring, was partly covered in the related workshop described in section 4.2. Methods like 'pilot tone' injection and other technical realizations can also be applied at linear light sources.

The last objective concerning beam loss localization and fast interlock generation could not be covered due to the COVID-19 crisis as the task leader could not arrange a workshop in a remote format.

7. Conclusion and Outlook

The Topical Workshops within the frame of ARIES-ADA had a high impact on the development of advanced beam instrumentation. World-leading experts participated in the workshops as well as newcomers, who now take over in the development of novel instrumentation; in this sense, a durable network was initialized. In most of the workshops, engineers participated as well; they contribute significantly to the success of any beam instrumentation but, in many cases, do not participate significantly in conferences. The mixture of these experts contributed to the very positive 'flavour' of the workshop and contribute to the development of accelerators. The relevance of such workshops can be measured through the interest shown for each event by the worldwide audience: 32 – 84 delegates for in-person meetings and 49 to 239 for remote meetings. In particular, for the in-person events, a familiar atmosphere was created with senior people who met young scientist engineers to force discussions about layout details and 'tricks', which usually are not discussed at large conferences, which is very helpful for designing and operating beam instrumentation successfully. The program could be adapted to the pandemic situation after some delay by remote meetings. This format led to a larger and broader spread amount of delegates; with the help of breakout rooms, some discussions and personal contacts could still be established.

The obtained collection of high-quality contributions serves as a comprehensive reference summarising the actual status of these fields and proposals for further developments as gained from experience at the various accelerator facilities. In this sense, the ARIES-ADA Network Activity is an essential contribution to the general accelerator R&D. Almost every objective described in the original proposal were addressed and led to enhanced network activities. Moreover, additional topics were discussed in dedicated workshops on scintillation screens and material and engineering issues, which widened the scope towards innovations.

The workshop results were summarised at several conferences and scientific publications for a larger audience. The program ARIES is now well-known to the beam instrumentation community.

It is recommended to continue such topical workshops in future, as it is an efficient way of knowledge transfer and related personal contact. This will lead to man-power saving collaborations that justify the financial budget invested in covering travel expenses for in-person meetings.

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9. Attachments

The summaries of the three individual workshops related with Deliverable 8.1 are attached in chronological order. As various authors wrote the reports, the style varies, but the text should introduce the workshop topic and the individual talks. More information is available at the individual slides and the references therein.

ARIES-ADA Topical Workshop

Simulation, Design & Operation of Ionization Profile Monitors

Darmstadt, Germany, 21st to 24th May, 2017

INDICO-site: <http://indico.gsi.de/event/5366/>

Workshop Summary

Organiser: Peter Forck, Mariuz Sapinski – GSI, and Kenichiro Satou – J-PARC

Organised by:

Sponsored by :

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme under Grant Agreement No 730871

Workshop introduction and goals

In May 2017, a Topical Workshop took place at GSI (Darmstadt, Germany) concerning 'Simulation, Design & Operation of Ionization Profile Monitors' with 33 international participants; the INDICO-site is <https://indico.gsi.de/event/5366/>. GSI organised it with support from J-PARC. The workshop comprises 18 talks related to the hardware, operational experiences and simulation tool for Ionization Profile Monitors design, operations. Moreover, the workshop included a guided tour at GSI and an entire session for hands-on possibilities for the newly developed simulation package IPMSim.

An Ionization Profile Monitor (IPM) is based on spatially resolving the ions or electrons generated from residual gas ionisation through beam impact. These monitors deliver the beam profile in a non-destructive manner with a spatial resolution of typically 50 μm and time gating down to the ten ns level. They are installed at both hadron synchrotrons and LINACs. Due to the increase in the beam power of future LINACs (e.g. at CERN, ESS, FAIR, ISIS), these IPMs will substitute the traditional invasive wire-based diagnostics. Even though the principle is well known, there are many technical challenges for the reliable operation of IPMs.

The experience and technical solutions from installations worldwide were presented by the experts in the field, with the results extensively discussed and the related contributions serving as a comprehensive catalogue of such systems.

One purpose of the workshop was to introduce the community to a recently completed simulation package called IPMSim (see <https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/IPMSim/>), which is freely accessible. This code was produced with the input of several experts to simulate the related physical processes (cross-section for electron and ion production) under various conditions (beam distribution, space charge, external field configurations) from non-relativistic beams at LINACs to highly energetic beams at synchrotrons. The code features a modern programming style, a user-friendly GUI and can easily be expanded to include new physical models and applications. The code is freely available, and its benchmarking was successfully demonstrated. Further extensions of the code (e.g. for Beam Induced Fluorescence Monitors) are currently included. Various laboratories produced different codes, a standard set of beam parameters were agreed on to perform such benchmarking between those codes. Possible experimental verifications of such simulations were put forward at this workshop.

This workshop acted as a follow-up to a previous workshop held at CERN in February 2016 <https://indico.cern.ch/event/491615/>. Due to the significant interest in this field, a third workshop will be executed at J-PARC (Tokai, Japan) in autumn 2018, see <https://conference-indico.kek.jp/indico/event/55/>.

The workshop was dedicated to the memorial of Dr. Bernd Dehning, who passed away in January 2017 due to fast-developing cancer disease. Bernd Dehning was in Germany in 1957. Starting in 1987 he worked at CERN Beam Instrumentation Group on transverse profile measurements and beam loss detection. He made many valuable contributions to the field of beam diagnostics and participated numerous conferences and workshops. Moreover, he supervised several master PhD theses. We lost an excellent scientist, a competent colleague, and a good friend.

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Session 1: Design and technologies I (chair: Mariusz Sapenski - GSI)

Preliminary Study on IPM for CADS Injector

Jun He, IHEP, Beijing, China

The talk summarises the present status of the IPM development, which serves as a prototype for the Chinese ADS and the neutron spallation source CSNS and the heavy-ion facility HIAF. The IPM detector consists of a round \varnothing 75 mm Multi-Channel Plate (MCP) with an optical readout. For calibration purposes, an Electron Generation Array (EGA) is installed. Jun He reported on the experiences at the LINAC with moderate vacuum pressures. The signal is sufficient and, due to the beam current, transverse size (standard deviation during the tests was $\sigma > 10$ mm), and bunch length, the space charge broadening is at an exceptional level without applying a magnetic field. Some operational challenges due to electromagnetic interference are reported and significant background contributions related to the test installation close to a beam dump. The latter should not be relevant for the installation at the foreseen locations within the LINAC sections.

Current status of the BGI profile monitor for the CERN PS based on the Timepix3 hybrid pixel detector

Swann Levasseur, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland

For the injector upgrade at CERN, new diagnostics are required to operate the high-brilliant beams required for the High Luminosity LHC beam parameters. An IPM for PS is under development. This IPM for the horizontal plane was recently installed and tested some weeks before the workshop. The IPM uses electron detection mode for a time resolution of about 1 ms in the integration mode (high resolution) and a turn-by-turn mode on the 1 μ s time scale with a storage capacity of 5000 turns. The vacuum pressure is in the order of 10^{-9} mbar. It is surrounded by a large dipole magnet commonly mounted together with the corresponding corrector dipoles to correct the proton beam closed orbit; this leads to a compact installation of only 80 cm insertion length.

In contrary to other IPMs, this monitor does not use an MCP but a silicon pixel detector. This so-called Timepix3 detector is a joint development of several high-energy physics and medical imaging groups. It consists of a 256 x 256 matrix of pixels with 55 x 55 μ m pixel size. This ASIC chip is fully equipped with readout digitalisation based on FPGA technology enabling several readout methods. Four Timepix3 chips are mounted to cover the required range for the transverse beam profile measurement. It is the first time that such a pixel detector and its active electronics is installed in a vacuum. Cooling of the electronics was an issue but could be solved; the detector is now in operation. First beam images are presented in the talk showing the potential of this readout technology.

GSI IPMs

Tino Giacomini, GSI, Darmstadt, Germany

Since several years, IPMs have been in operation at GSI synchrotron and storage rings using an ion detection mode. The detection is based on a 100 x 50 mm Chevron MCP read by a wire array of 2.1 mm spacing. The time resolution of the related electronics is 10 ms. To increase the spatial resolution, an IPM under development uses a phosphor readout. A camera performs the digitalisation in the so-called high resolution mode with about 10 ms time resolution. In future, fast photodetectors are foreseen for a turn-by-turn readout (due to the vacuum pressure in the order of 10^{-11} mbar, the signal strength is only sufficient for ion beams). The high voltage of the monitor's field cage can be connected such that alternatively ion or electron detection is possible. The IPM installation comprises large aperture dipole magnets (about 50 cm aperture) and corresponding corrector dipoles, leading to an insertion length of about 2.5 m. The mechanical design considerations, the software status and the first experiences from bench tests are reported. A monitor

without a magnetic field (and hence with ion detection mode only) is installed in the GSI storage ring ESR and at FZ-Jülich COSY ring (see below for the talk by Christian Böhme). Both installations show good performance and are well suited to monitor the beam cooling process.

For the MCP calibration, GSI has very positive experiences using a UV lamp (deuteron lamp, emission maximum 115 nm) mounted outside of the vacuum chamber and illuminating the MPCs via MgF₂ window.

Session 2: Design and technologies II (chair: James Storey - CERN)

IPM Experience at SNS

Alexander Aleksandrov, SNS, Oak Ridge, USA

In the SNS accumulator ring, a test IPM is installed. The installation aims for a turn-by-turn resolution, corresponding to about 1 μ s for the full beam of up to 10¹⁴ protons. A movable channeltron is used for the detection. To enable the required time resolution for the electron detection mode, a very high electric field is foreseen with an electrode voltage up to 120 kV. This high voltage requires a dedicated design and special insulation. Problems are reported related to signal oscillations for the electron detection mode, which depend on the field cage voltage. A large-aperture dipole magnet is installed; dedicated correctors are not required as existing steerers can correct the closed orbit distortions. However, the IPM required large insertion space and was very expensive. An ion detection mode does not require a magnet; however, the achievable time resolution does not fulfil the turn-by-turn readout requirement.

Presently, the IPM is not used anymore as it is a too expensive device and difficult to operate. Instead, SNS is in favour of an electron beam scanner mounted in the accumulator ring. For the detection in the LINAC, a laser wire scanner is in preparation. Photo-detachment is a suitable method for the accelerated H⁻ atoms, which provide transverse and longitudinal diagnostics. The laser scanner layout is briefly discussed.

Supersonic gas-jet beam profile monitor

Hao Zhang, Cockcroft Institute, Warrington, UK

For several applications, e.g. at low current medical synchrotrons, the signal strength of an IPM operated with the ambient vacuum pressure is too low. To increase the gas density in the interaction region, a gas jet can be used instead. At Cockcroft Institute, an IPM with a supersonic gas jet is under development. The gas jet is created by a nozzle enabling a supersonic expansion to create cold gas with a defined velocity profile. Two skimmers form a gas jet that interacts with the beam. The jet is caught by a chamber extension opposite to the nozzle and efficiently pumped by a turbo-molecular pump. The arrangement barely influences the ambient pressure of the vacuum chamber. The gas-jet properties are investigated with a movable gauge proving the correct supersonic expansion and the skimmer functionality. The layout of the gas system and the IPM is presented. The device was extensively tested with a low current electron beam. The same type of gas-jet can be used for the Beam Induced Fluorescence (BIF) detection, where an image-intensified camera can monitor photons from the excited gas (e.g. nitrogen). The latter system is foreseen as a profile monitor at LHC. The possibility of gas-jet focusing by Fresnel zone plates is proposed in the talk.

Session 3: Operational issues I (chair: James Zagel - Fermilab)

Current status of the optical-based SPS and LHC BGI Profile Monitors

James Storey, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland

The IPM installed at CERN SPS and LHC is a bit older construction. It uses electron detection mode amplified by an MCP and P46 phosphor. For compact installation, the phosphor is deposited on a prism used as a mirror to guide the light towards a camera. A magnet of 200 mT is used; the insertion space is not an issue in this

synchrotron. Some recent technical problems are reported. In particular, the ageing of the MCP is a problem as well as a degradation of the phosphor efficiency. An Electron Generation Array (EGA) is used for the MCP calibration. For the nominal LHC beam in SPS some image broadening is observed, calling for an increase of the magnetic field to at least 1 T. Moreover, a beam-based heating by wake-fields is observed for such high current beams, which destroyed one prims. The main goal for the near future is an improvement of the user software to enable operational usage.

For the intense beams in LHC, further upgrade, e.g. a stronger magnetic field, is urgently required as the accelerated beam's space charge is so large that significant image distortion is expected even in the case of electron detection. It might be required to change the IPM installation significantly.

News from J-PARC: the system, the data and the simulation code

Kenichirou Satou, J-PARC, Japan

The contribution discusses the Main Ring IPM installation. The monitor comprises an electric field cage operated by a relative voltage up to 50 kV. The MCP signal is read by a strip array of 2.5 mm pitch. The MCP calibration is realised by an Electron Generation Array (EGA). An electromagnet surrounds the IPM with 250 mT field strength. Corrector magnets are installed close by to correct the proton beam closed orbit. The magnet design is discussed in the talk, including the requirements for the field quality and the 'cross talk' between the main magnet and the close-by corrector magnet with inverse field direction.

A pulse mode operation was recently commissioned, which allows a turn-by-turn reading without too high risks for an MCP destruction; a duty factor of 1 % is typically chosen (1ms profile measurements per second); the MCP lifetime should increase than be roughly a factor of 100. This setup is comparable to the one designed by Fermilab. A beam-based calibration was realised by scanning the beam across the detection area, which might offer some significant advantages compared to using an EGA. With those advanced methods in operation, the IPM is used frequently for beam alignments.

Operational experience of the electron collecting IPM at AGS/BNL

Chuyu Liu, BNL, Brookhaven, USA

BNL has many years of experience in the construction and operation of IPMs, and several variants were tested. Electron detection is nowadays used in the AGS and RHIC. After amplification by a single MCP, the electrons are collected by an anode board of 64 channels of 0.5 mm strip width. The total detection width is 3.2 cm only. To increase the signal strength, a controllable vacuum valve is used with an inlet of CO₂ gas. The IPM is surrounded by a magnet to guide the residual gas electrons. One operational problem is related to a beam movement larger than the detection widths of 3.2 cm, which might lead to a wrong interpretation of the profile reading. Beam-based calibration by a moving beam across the detection area is used at BNL. Besides profile measurements on a turn-by-turn basis, the system is used for beta-function measurements.

Session 4: Operational issues II (chair: Alexander Aleksandrov - SNS)

Beam Profile Monitors at Fermilab, a 2017 update

James Zagel, Fermilab, Batavia, USA

IPMs are installed in all synchrotrons at Fermilab. They use electron detection mode and a Chevron MCP of typical 100 x 100 mm size for single-particle amplification. The readout is performed by a wire array on a Printed Circuit Board with a 0.5 mm strip width. In the booster, no magnetic field is required related to the large beam size. In the Main Ring, permanent magnets are installed, offering a more compact installation compared to electromagnets. Several improvements are discussed in the contribution.

The operational usage is mainly related to injection optimisation, which is performed by turn-by-turn detections. Switching of the electric field is required to enhance the MCP lifetime, which was recently realised by the modulation of the guiding electric field. A performant user interface is available, allowing the usage by non-expert during daily operation.

The efficiency and spatial homogeneity of the MCPs is an essential topic for the image reproduction of the beam profile. Fermilab operates a dedicated test chamber for MCPs; a filament of a vacuum gauge acts as a source of electrons. Test results concerning the MCP characterisation are discussed in the contribution.

Analysis of optical IPM data

Mariusz Sapinski, GSI, Darmstadt, Germany

The contribution concerns the data analysis for the recently installed IPM at CERN LHC; the hardware is described in the talk by James Storey, see above. Due to the small size of $\sigma \approx 300 \mu\text{m}$ and the large bunch current, space charge effects are dominant, even in the case of electron detection with a magnetic field of $\approx 200 \text{ mT}$. This leads to an image deformation, which has a non-linear dependence on the profile shape and bunch current.

The second source of image deformation is related to the secondary ion suppression wires (mounted opposite to the MCP), optical system, and camera noise. The latter manifests itself in strips on the image and interleaving products of the Thermo Scientific Charge Injection Device (CID) camera. To eliminate the regular readout pattern with a 25 Hz noise structure, image reconstruction methods were tested. The application of an FFT filter was only partly successful as frequency mixing products were not entirely compensated by the FFT filter. As a second method, the deconvolution using a calculated Point Spread Function of the entire system was applied. The work is ongoing, so no defined conclusion can be drawn for the time being concerning the best operational usage.

Operational Experience with the Ionization Beam Profile Monitor at COSY

Christian Böhme, FZJ-COSY, Jülich, Germany

FZJ and GSI commonly developed the IPM hardware at COSY. Ion detection is applied at COSY as the beam current for most experiments is low such that space effects are not expected; therefore, no magnetic field is required. The monitor comprises an electric field cage optimised for a homogeneous electric field in the interaction region, uses a Chevron MCP with a phosphor readout by a standard CCD camera with a GigE interface. The related data acquisition software is based on Labview, and a reasonable performant user interface is available.

Reflections of the light from the phosphor at the vacuum chamber wall lead to some image distortions; however, this could be subtracted from the correct beam image. Some modifications of the phosphor thickness or efficiency occurred for unknown reasons. In future, a software upgrade using EPICS is planned.

Beam Ionisation Profile Monitor Proposal for ELENA

Pierre Grandemagne, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland

The ELENA ring at CERN is used to decelerate anti-protons from 5.3 MeV to 100 keV with the application of electron cooling at intermediate and final energy. The main goal for the IPM is the observation during the entire cycle. The recently constructed mechanics is depicted. In contrary to other IPMs, a Z-stack (triple) MCP is used to increase the amplification. Moreover, a gas injection system for CO₂ is required to increase the signal strength for the low current anti-proton beam; the related average vacuum pollution in the ring stays at an acceptable level (below 9 %); no significant decrease of the beam lifetime was observed. The evolution of the beam profile was recorded with sufficient statistical accuracy in the case of a CO₂ gas inlet.

Session 5: Simulation I (chair: Kenichirou Satou – J-PARC)

Summary of the outcome of the first workshop

Mariusz Sapinski, GSI, Darmstadt, Germany

The talk summarises the results from the preceding workshop called ‘IPM Simulation kick-off Workshop’, INDOC site <https://indico.cern.ch/event/491615/>, which was organised by CERN and held on 3rd to 4th of May 2016 in Geneva. An almost complete survey of the existing simulation codes of the space charge broadening for IPMs was executed at this workshop. A contribution to the conference IBIC in 2016 summarises the status [1]; the table from this publication is shown below. The publication contains an excellent overview of the various methods used in those codes; some comments are included in the paragraphs below related to the individual codes. Compared to the status of the first workshop in March 2016, some progress has been achieved up to now: Several codes were compared to assess the influence on theoretical assumptions and numerical accuracy. Some of the codes are benchmarked with respect to each other using the same input parameters. This led to debugging and significant improvements of some codes. Most participants of the preceding workshop attended the actual workshop, leading to an intensified discussion on the simulation methods.

It is a solid proposal to focus the investigations towards a single code development. The package IPMSim3D is best suited for this purpose, as it uses only freeware and is written in the performant language Python [2]. The code is available at <https://gitlab.com/IPMSim/Virtual-IPM> and the documentation at <https://ipmsim.gitlab.io/Virtual-IPM/>. Dominik Vilsmeier reported on the code layout in a separate talk; see below. The leadership is in the hand of GSI, and most participants explain their interest to participate in the joint development with a contribution to the code development. However, for comparison, some of the existing codes will be maintained by the corresponding institutes.

Tabulated overview on IPM simulation codes in the year 2016, published with more details in [1]

Name/Lab	Language	Ionization	Guiding field	shape	Beam field	Tracking
GSI code	C++	simple DDCS	uniform E,B	parabolic 3D	3D analytic relativ.	numeric R-K 4 th order
PyECLOUD-BGI /CERN	python	realistic DDCS	uniform E,B	Gauss 3D	2D analytic relativ. only	analytic
FNAL	MATLAB	simple SDCS	3D map E,B	arbitrary	3D numeric relativ. (E and B)	num. MATLAB rel. eq. of motion
ISIS	C++	at rest	CST map E only	arbitrary (CST)	2D numeric (CST) non-relativ.	numeric Euler 2 nd order
IFMIF	C++	at rest	Lorenz-3E map E only	General Gauss	numeric (Lorenz-3E) non-relativ.	
ESS	MATLAB	at rest	uniform E,B	Gauss 3D	3D numeric (MATLAB) relativ.	numeric MATLAB R-K
IPMSim3D /J-PARC	python	realistic DDCS	2D/3Dmap E, B	Gauss 3D	2D numeric (SOR) relativ. only	numeric R-K 4 th order

[1] M. Sapinski et al., "Ionization Profile Monitor Simulations - Status and Future Plans", in Proc. 5th Int. Beam Instrumentation Conf. (IBIC'16), Barcelona, Spain, Sep. 2016, pp. 520-523.

<https://doi.org/doi:10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2016-TUPG71>

[2] D. Vilsmeier, P. Forck, and M. Sapinski, "A modular Application for IPM simulations", in Proc. IBIC'17, Grand Rapids, MI, USA, Sep. 2017, pp. 335-338.

<http://jacow.org/ibic2017/papers/wepcc07.pdf>

IPM simulations in Fermilab

Randy Thurman-Keup, Fermilab, Batavia, USA

The code at Fermilab is written in MATLAB as it was initially foreseen to be used by the experienced programmer only. Several advanced features are included now. Single differential cross sections are implemented to describe the electron generation process. The tracking part for the residual gas electrons uses full relativistic equations; a Runge-Kutta algorithm will be implemented soon. Since the proton bunches' field is evaluated externally and imported, the bunch shape is not limited to any functional form. Interpolated field maps are used for guiding electrical and magnetic fields. The contribution discusses several interesting simulation results and their physical interpretation.

One recent topic is related to the switching requirement to prolong the lifetime of the MPCs by the modified potential at the electrodes, as mentioned in the talk by James Zagel. To fix the related parameters, the code calculates the electric field and the electron trajectories in the switch-off state. Recently, the functionality was experimentally demonstrated.

In addition, the code was successfully applied for the simulation of the electron trajectories for a laser wire scanner (photo-detachment from an H⁻ beam, available at the Fermilab LINAC) and an electron beam scanner (deflection of external 60 keV electrons by the beam space charge) as installed in the main injector.

Space charge studies for the ESS Ionization Profile Monitor

Francesca Belloni, CEA/Saclay, Saclay, France

Motivated by the layout of IPMs for the ESS LINAC, a code was developed at CEA/Saclay to test possible image deformations for the nominal beam parameters. Due to the enormous beam power, non-intersecting profile detection is required. The code solves the classical equation of motion for any charged particle in an electromagnetic field. A Gaussian distribution is assumed in the rest frame for the proton beam and then Lorentz-transformed to the lab frame. Non-linear Runge-Kutta tracking is applied. The code is written in MATLAB.

For the ESS IPMs, ion detection is foreseen, as the insertion space does not allow for extra magnet installation. Possible image deformations are discussed in the contribution. For the typical beam parameters, acceptable deformation is achieved if a relatively high electric field of 300 kV/m is applied. This high voltage might lead to a technical challenge for the required high voltage.

Session 6: Simulation II (chair: Jacques Marroncle – CEA/Saclay)

Follow up on old GSI code

Serban Udrea, GSI, Darmstadt, Germany

Starting in the year 2004, a code was developed at GSI for the IPM and Beam Induced Fluorescence (BIF) simulations. It is based on an analytic solution for parabolic transverse distribution and either coasting or bunched beams using elliptical coordinates. The advantage of the analytic solution is the significantly faster

processing time. However, electrical boundaries cannot be included, e.g. related to the vacuum pipe. Tracking is performed by the Runge-Kutta method. The guiding electric and magnetic fields must be homogeneous. The code is written in C++ using a nowadays obsolete Borland compiler. The package has a reasonably good graphical user interface: Input parameters are well-arranged, and intermediate results are depicted. The output is stored in several formats.

Several bugs of the code are discovered during the benchmark period, which is corrected, or will be corrected soon. The GSI code will be available for some time as it allows more straightforward usage; even though the IPMSim package is more performant and better maintainable,

Simulations and Studies of IPMs at ISIS

Chris Wilcox, ISIS, Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, UK

Contrary to other IPM realisations with a rectangular electric field box, a unique mechanical arrangement is realised at the ISIS synchrotron. The field forming electrodes are longitudinally shifted with respect to the detectors for the horizontal and vertical plane. This allows a compact installation for both planes. As caused by a resulting longitudinal electric field component, the movement of the residual gas ions follows a curved trajectory. This results in a more complex simulation of the space charge induced image broadenings. The monitor uses ion detection by an array of 40 channeltrons.

The ISIS code uses field maps generated by 3-dim CST calculations for the external guiding electric field and the bunched beam, allowing for arbitrary proton beam distributions. A homogeneous residual ion distribution is generated within the beam volume; the ion tracking is performed by a 2nd order Euler method to solve the equation of motion. The code is realised in a C++. Post-processing is applied to achieve realistic proton beam distribution by weighting the initially homogeneous start distribution.

Code validation is performed at a transfer line IPM by comparison to the profile measurement by an SEM-grid. Due to the more complex monitor arrangement, a direct comparison to simulation results obtained for other accelerators is difficult.

A new, modular framework for IPM simulations

Dominik Vilsmeier, GSI, Darmstadt, Germany

It was one of the workshop goals to introduce the participants to the recent development of the newly developed code IPMSim (or alternatively called Virtual-IPM) at GSI. The code is available at <https://gitlab.com/IPMSim/Virtual-IPM> and the documentation at <https://ipmsim.gitlab.io/Virtual-IPM/>. The primary motivation was to focus the simulation efforts on one code, which is commonly developed; GSI will overtake the maintenance issues. The code is written in Python 3, including the scientific packages 'numpy' and 'scipy'.

The figure below shows the global architecture of the software package. For electron generation, the simulation uses realistic double differential cross-sections. For the residual gas electron or ions tracking, a Runge-Kutta or Boris algorithm can be chosen. External electric and guiding magnetic fields can either be assumed as homogeneous, or maps can be imported from field solvers such as CST and COMSOL. The field of the proton or ion beam can be generated either by analytical descriptions (e.g. for Gaussian- or parabolic distributions) or is calculated via a 3-dim Poisson solver. This is important for 'exotic' beam distributions, e.g. for beams generated by multi-turn injection or cooled beam resulting in non-Gaussian distributions. For the case of an IPM simulation, the residual gas electrons or ions are stopped at a barrier. The code can simulate the situation relevant for Beam Induced Fluorescence, where photons are emitted after a specific (exponentially distributed) lifetime. Moreover, the code can calculate the field by multiple beams, e.g. the merged electron and proton beam for the planned, hollow electron lens at High-Luminosity LHC.

A graphical user interface allows for well-controlled input parameter choice and can depict intermediate results, e.g. single electron trajectories. The user can specify several output formats; e.g. a map comparing

the initial and final electron or ion coordinates is also available. Further modules can be included in the package on demand. The IPMSim package was benchmarked versus other codes. Some hand-on demonstration followed the talk to motivate the package usage, call for comments, and eventually contributions to the development.

The modular components of the IPMSim package

Session 7: Special presentations (chair: Peter Forck – GSI)

Storage of ions at low energies at GSI and Precision Experiments over 12 Decades

Frank Herfurth, GSI, Darmstadt, Germany

The talk intended to introduce recent developments at the GSI facilities dedicated to highly charged ions stored at low energies. The HITRAP facility is discussed, where heavy ions are accelerated with the UNIVAC & SIS facility to typically 400 MeV/u and stripped to a high charge state. Then they are decelerated in the ESR storage ring, where an electron and stochastic cooling is applied. A LINAC further decelerates the beam down to 100 keV/u to enable the injection into a trap. Here cooling is applied by collision with cold helium gas. Finally, the ions can be used for atomic physics experiments, e.g. for basic research in additional Penning traps to measure the g-factor of those highly charged ions. The actual achievements concerning the accelerators and experimental setup at GSI are reported. This type of cold, highly charged ion generation is compared to achievements using an EBIS ion source.

A low energy storage ring will be installed at GSI soon, a refurbishment of the CRYING from Manne Siegbahn Institute in Stockholm. It fits well into the GSI facility as highly charged ions will be stored, cooled and decelerated. Atomic physics investigations will be possible, e.g., measuring the Lamb-shift of highly charged ions as a precision study of QED.

The talks served as an introduction to the guided tour at GSI.

IPM Profile Reconstruction using Neural Networks

Rahul Singh, GSI, Darmstadt, Germany

IPMs with ion detection is realised when insertion space is limited (e.g. at LINACs), leading to a significant image broadening. However, even for the case of electron detection, a magnetic guiding field of about 300 mT might not be sufficient to guaranty an undistorted electron transport (e.g. for small beams at LHC). Moreover, the initial velocity of the electron, as generated by the kinematic of the collision with the beam particles, leads to some deformation of the measured profile. As shown by various simulation codes, the measured distribution might deviate in a non-linear manner from the initial beam profile. Non-linear reconstruction techniques could be applied for these beam parameters. Machine Learning by Artificial Neural Network (ANN) could be an appropriate method to achieve an efficient reconstruction. Using the available simulation results as generated, e.g. by IPMSim, a basis for the ANN training can be generated on a considerable large span of beam parameters such as transverse and longitudinal beam distribution as well as beam currents. The contribution discusses the basics of supervised ANN and shows a route for realising a matched network and its parameter. First tests were executed using a dedicated MATLAB toolbox applying various ANN parameters.

The novel method of Machine Learning by supervised ANN seems to be a forward-looking technology for such image reconstruction and will be investigated intensively in the future.

- ARIES-ADA Topical Workshop
- Scintillation Screens and Optical Technology for transverse Profile Measurements
 - Krakow, Poland, April 1 to 3, 2019
 - INDICO-site: <https://indico.cern.ch/event/765975/>
 - Workshop Summary

Editors: Enrico Bravin - CERN, Peter Forck - GSI, Ubaldo Iriso - ALBA, Rhodri Jones - CERN, Gero Kube – DESY, Thibaut Lefevre - CERN, Beata Walasek-Höhne - GSI, Adriana Wawrzyniak - SOLARIS

- Organized by:
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- **Workshop introduction and goal**

For many decades, scintillation screens have been widely used for transverse beam profile measurements in transfer lines. They offer a two-dimensional beam image, i.e. possible correlations between the horizontal and vertical plane can be visualized. Generally, the screen is inserted in the beam pass, and, for many beam parameters, they are destructive and disable further controlled beam transport. In most cases, inorganic scintillation materials are used.

Even though this method for profile measurement seems to be well-known, there is a significant increase of interest in the underlying physics, technical realization and application. One recent application at FEL facilities is based on the alternatively used Optical Transition Radiation (OTR) failure. For typical beam parameter at FEL facilities, it is related to the emission of coherent OTR for longitudinal bunch lengths in the order of an optical wavelength in combination with the small transverse beam size. The scintillation screen emits the light incoherently with some time delay in the order of several ns. On the other hand, saturation effect can occur, leading to wrong image reproduction. To achieve the required spatial resolution, a specially designed optical system is required.

For hadron accelerators, the method is used frequently, mainly related to two-dimensional beam image monitoring and its simple technical realization. However, thermal quenching and permanent radiation damage might lead to a decrease in the light yield, particularly at the beam centre. The effect depends significantly on the used scintillation material, i.e. an appropriate choice of material is of great importance.

In the last years, a significant development took place concerning inorganic scintillator materials related to their usage in high energy physics detectors, medical imaging and homeland security. The technical development is accompanied by an increase concerning the theoretical modelling and understanding of the related multi-step physical processes.

Optics and camera technologies is another technical topic where significant improvements and novel applications are developed.

The workshop's goal is to discuss those issues and benefit from the knowledge and experiences in other laboratories. Experts from the scintillator material research participated in explaining some of the empirical results obtained during accelerator operation. Representatives from scintillator production companies reported on novel materials and their production chain. The layout of optics and cameras were discussed by industrial partners. Experts from the accelerator facilities discussed their system layout, material choice, radiation hardness issues and reported on (positive or sometimes negative) experiences during beam operation.

The topic is essential for all types of accelerators! Representatives from electron LINAC and synchrotrons, hadron facilities and laser wake-field accelerators participated.

The workshop took place from the 1st to 3rd of April 2019 in Krakow, Poland and included a guided tour at the light source SOLARIS. Forty-nine people participated in the workshop, among them three from the USA, one from Asia and four representatives from European industry. Significantly more people applied for participation than initially anticipated; however, the chosen conference location does not allow for more attendees. The program consists of thirty talks and three discussion sessions. Moreover, three industrial participants presented their products in a booth, triggering intensive discussion during coffee breaks. Some sponsoring by industry reduced the cost for participants. The workshop INDICO-site is <https://indico.cern.ch/event/765975/>. GSI and Solaris organized the workshop with significant contributions by ALBA, CERN and DESY.

Due to the general relevance, the subject of this workshop was presented for a larger audience as an invited talk at the beam instrumentation conference IBIC 2019 (B. Walasek-Höhne, P. Forck, K. Höhne, R. Ischebeck, and G. Kube, "Screens for High Precision Measurements", in Proc. 8th Int. Beam Instrumentation Conf. (IBIC'19), Malmö, Sweden, Sep. 2019, pp. 242-248. doi:10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2019-TUBO01)

- **Session 1: Scintillator Physics and Technology (chair P. Forck)**
- **Profile Measurements with Scintillators: Requirements and application at accelerators**

Gero Kube, DESY, Hamburg, Germany

The talk serves as an overview concerning the usage of scintillation screens at accelerators for transverse profile determination. The general scheme, namely the insertion of a scintillator disk and the observation with a camera was applied from the beginning of accelerator development and seems to be very simple technology. The light is generated close to the beam particle's trajectory, which results in a beam image. However, scintillation is a multi-step process starting with the generation of fast electrons by the primary beam interaction, followed by thermalization of the electrons and the capture in luminescence centres.

For high energetic beams the primary collision can result in a high velocity of the first stage electrons, which has to be considered in case of high resolution small beam detection. For an ion impact, the ionization density might be very high (compared to the typical usage for medical imaging or for HEP experiments); a summarizing comparison of typical properties for medical and HEP applications compared to the beam instrumentation usage is given in the last slide. A collection of typically scintillator material is given and their properties are summarized. Detailed test of various materials at MAMI and DESY are depicted and compared to OTR measurements. Results obtained at XFEL are shown, the so called 'smoke rings', but are discussed in more detail in a second talk by the author.

The resolution limits by the optics setup and in particular by the observation geometry are given in terms of an overview using instructive plots, more details on the limiting factors are discussed in several other talks.

- **Introduction to scintillator physics**

Weronika Wolszczak, Delft University of Technology, Netherlands

The subject of the talk is a general introduction to the physics of the scintillation process: As a first step by the primary particle interaction, fast electrons are liberated, which then collide with the electrons in the conducting band leading to a thermalization. The slowed down electrons are then captured to either traps or luminescence centres by impurities or crystal defect. The observed light in the optical region is then emitted by the spontaneous decay of these excited states. The holes created by the primary beam interaction thermalize as well and serve as the partner for the exciton generation.

The properties of the intrinsic scintillator type (like NaCl, KCl and KBr), based on exciton or colour centre emission is discussed in terms of emission and absorption wavelength. The importance of self-trap excitons is pointed out together with their temperature dependence, which can be reduced by a factor 10 between LN₂ and room temperature. For doped scintillators the emission properties can be quite different as they are greatly influenced on the doping species; as an example the emission wavelength for various types is discussed as well as their temperature dependence.

To model the generation of luminescence centres, the interaction of the primary particle has to be considered to estimate the ratio of exciton and self-trapped hole generation compared to the dopant excitation. This is important to model any non-proportionality (i.e. a non-linear behaviour between the deposited energy by the primary particle and the light output). Examples for different scintillators are discussed for γ and electron impact. This leads to different densities of the ionization along the primary particle trajectory with a radius up to the 100 nm range and include significant time dependences. The effect can be simulated by Monte-Carlo methods and it is shown that it depends on the primary electron energy with a different scaling for the various materials; the effect was explained in the talk (and is of importance for the usage as beam instrumentation). The related experimental techniques are briefly summarized.

- **Usage and technology of fast scintillators**

Etiennette Auffray, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland

The motivation of this talk is related to the requirements of High Energy Physics detectors like of CERN's CMS and LHCb in terms of high rate capability and radiation hardness. A fast decay time of the scintillator is required to distinguish between different hits and enable high spatial resolving track reconstruction. But also for medical PET tomography the fast timing properties enable a more precise reconstruction by efficient background reduction. The related properties of the scintillator are discussed; beside a fast decay time, a large amount of photons increases the accuracy of the arrival time determination. Additionally, the scintillator geometry and the photo detector time response can be optimized.

The scintillator properties can be influenced by the doping ions; this is discussed for the case of YAG:Ce using the technique of co-doping with an addition of e.g. Mg to the main Ce doping (e.g. to decrease the afterglow contribution). The light transport with respect to timing issues are discussed with nano-structural modification of the crystal surface. The timing properties of different scintillators are compared and design criteria for fast timing achievements are given. The application for calorimeters at HEP detectors and PET scanners are discussed.

Radiation damage is a further challenge for HEP detectors. The creating of traps leads to a decrease of light yield as the electrons or holes are captured as a competing process to the original luminescence levels. Moreover, the absorption increases by transitions to the trap levels. It is shown that a certain recovery of damage occurs with pronounced temperature dependences. The radiation hardness is influenced by the dopant as a comparison of garnets shows. The related parameters of scintillating fibres are discussed as well showing the progress obtained in the last years. A recent article summarizes the actual status of the research: C. Dujardin, E. Auffray, E. Bourret-Courchesne, P. Dorenbos, P. Lecoq, M. Nikl, A. N. Vasil'ev, A. Yoshikawa, and R.-Y. Zhu, '*Needs, Trends, and Advances in Inorganic Scintillators*', IEEE Transaction on Nuclear Science, Vol. 65, No. 8, August 2018, page 1977 – 1997.

The talk concluded with the announcement of the conference series SCINT, organized by the experts in inorganic scintillator design, production and usage.

- **Production and use of inorganic scintillators**

Jiri Parizek, CRYTUR, Turnov, Czech Republic

CRYTUR is one of the suppliers for inorganic scintillators, with a tradition dating back to the 1940th as a university institute. Beside the production of standard scintillators, a strong R&D participation in recent developments is the strength of this company. They host the production chain of various type of scintillator (YAG, LuAG, YAP, PWO etc.) with a great variety of dopants.

The production method is discussed showing the different steps to achieve the required quality and homogeneous scintillator size. Quality assurance using typical material characterization methods is a major topic to maintain the high quality production. The properties of screens, as used in beam instrumentation, are discussed showing the feasibility of production of thin screens. In the case of YAG this can be a free-standing versions (down to 50 μm for 50 mm diameter and 20 μm for 10 mm diameter), designs with a ring support or on a substrate (down to 10 μm). Moreover, fibres can be produced. The response to X-rays (10 to 100 keV) and the temperature dependence are shown for different materials as well as results from radiation hardness tests are discussed.

New materials are developed (partly in collaboration with research institutes) like GAAG, CRY19 CRY060 etc. for the optimization of light yield or fast decay time. The corresponding powders are available as well.

Entire systems for X- and γ -ray imaging are produced and an example for the achievable resolution was discussed.

- **Session 2: Cameras, Optics and Electronics I (chair E. Bravin)**

Introduction to relevant optical technologies and screen resolution & PSF investigations

Stephen Gibson, Royal Holloway University of London, United Kingdom

Acquiring precise images of a particle beam is a difficult task, this presentation illustrates the main challenges and the state of the art methods used in the field.

Beam images are used to extract the beam size, the transverse distribution (profile) and position. First there is the interaction between the beam and a radiator (e.g. scintillating screen, or OTR radiator), then the transport of the light through an optical system, then the raw image is acquired on camera. The camera images may then need post processing in order to remove artefacts introduced by the radiator or the optical system. At the end the real beam distribution is obtained.

The light generated inside scintillators is affected by refraction, so the apparent size of a particle beam depends on the angle of observation and the thickness of the screen itself, optimization of the parameters and correction of the effect are required.

It is usually impossible to observe the radiator at right angle; this implies depth of field issues (only part of the radiator can be focused sharply). Schiempflug solved this problem by tilting the lens in front of the camera so that all the points of the screen are focused on the plane of the sensor. This technique allows sharp images of the whole radiator, but still requires post processing to correct for the non-uniform magnification.

Optical systems are usually designed and optimised using ray tracing simulation tools, these allow the precise quantification of all sorts of aberrations. Calibration targets on the real optical system are also used to identify image distortions and tune the correction algorithms. Telecentric lenses can be used to compensate the non-uniform magnification of tilted screens.

Another important effect is the diffraction of the light in the optical system. The combination of aberrations and diffraction result in the so called point-spread-function, i.e. the size of the spot of light generated by a point source. Diffraction is well described by the Fraunhofer theory. If the point spread function is known, it can be de-convoluted from the raw images increasing the sharpness.

X-Rays from synchrotron radiation are usually imaged using pinhole cameras, a trade-off between resolution and diffraction is needed for the size of the pinhole.

In some cases multiple radiations can be overlapped, e.g. scintillation and OTR. In some cases it is possible to use the different time profiles of the radiations to separate them, e.g. the OTR can be discarded if the scintillation light is acquired with a very short time delay (OTR is instantaneous while scintillation has long decay times).

Overview on camera sensor technology

Walter Tutsch, PCO, Germany

A global overview of the available solid state camera technology is presented. The common basis of all different technologies is the photodiode that collects the charges liberated by the photons. The way the charge of the photodiode is read out differs then from one technology to the other.

In CCD sensors the charge is first simultaneously shifted into a storage area, the charges of each column of the storage area are shifted one by one toward the read out register. On its turn the cells of the read out register is shifted horizontally to the ADC. In this way all the pixels are digitized by the same ADC and it is relatively easy to create a uniform response over the whole sensor area. The disadvantage is that the readout is slow and the production is costly as it requires high grade silicon. The use of high grade silicon results in low dark current so long exposures are possible.

The main CCD producer (SONY, JP) has announced the discontinuation of the CCDs production in favour of CMOS sensors in 2017. In the EMCCD the sensitivity of a standard CCD is increased by adding an electron multiplication stage (limited avalanche regime) before the output amplifier.

CMOS sensors have been around for as long as CCDs but until recently were low cost, low performance sensors used in household appliances. The technology has been improved greatly and scientific CMOS (sCMOS) sensors have now matched and surpassed the performance of the CCD. The sCMOS are based on a complex pixel design with usually 5 transistors, w.r.t. the 3 transistors of the base CMOS design. This allows reducing the readout noise of the pixels, dominated by the thermal noise of the floating diffusion capacity, by the so called correlated double sampling technique. Readout noise of the order of 1 electron can be achieved w.r.t. the ~20 electrons of standard CMOS. High dynamic range with 16 bits digitization is also achieved in sCMOS by combining two 11 bits ADCs (a single 16 bit ADC would require too much power for an image sensor).

The complex design of the CMOS pixel reduces the silicon area available for light collection (filling factor). This effect can be reduced by using micro lenses on each pixel to focus the light on the sensitive part of the pixel or by illuminating the sensor on the back side (this requires the silicon chip to be thinned). sCMOS sensors offer high resolution, high sensitivity, high dynamic range, high frame rates, low readout noise and flexibility in the readout (multi-tap, area of interest etc.).

High resolution and high speed result in a high data rate. A new standard: "CameraLink HS" has been developed and can cope with many Gbit/s transmission in a scalable way (scalable multi-channel configuration).

Image intensifiers can be used to image very faint sources or to obtain very fast shutter times. Image intensifiers give better results when coupled to sensitive cameras, the sCMOS cameras suit perfectly this task.

CMOS and sCMOS sensors are taking over the market for image sensors and offer better performances than CCDs or EMCCD in almost all cases. The only case where CCDs are still superior is for very long exposure times thanks to the much lower dark current compared to CMOS and sCMOS.

- **Session 3: Cameras, Optics and Electronics II (chair R. Jones)**

Normalization, methods and equipment for testing cameras for imaging scintillation screens

Krzysztof Chrzanowski, Inframet, Poland

This talk focused on presenting standards that would allow beam instrumentalists to correctly compare their optical systems. Although there is no standard for testing cameras for scintillation screens, the EMVA-1288 (European Machine Vision Association) standard was cited as being the most appropriate, as requirements for machine vision cameras are similar to those for imaging scintillation screens. The EMVA standard does not describe a particular set-up in detail but presents a series of recommendations for the following:

1. Measurement of sensitivity, linearity and non-uniformity using a homogeneous monochromatic light source
2. Measurement of the temperature dependency of the dark current
3. Spectral measurements of the quantum efficiency over the whole range of wavelength to which the sensor is sensitive (relative spectral sensitivity).

Inframet provides two test stations based on this standard, one for testing camera cores or imaging sensors, and another for testing complete camera systems. In addition to EMVA-1288 parameters the Inframet test stations can measure radiometric parameters (such as Noise Equivalent Illuminance/Irradiance, Non Uniformity, Signal to Noise Ratio, dead pixels and 3D Noise) as well as Imaging parameters (such as MTF, resolution, Minimal Resolvable Contrast, crosstalk, blooming and FOV). From the point of view of test equipment, the type of imaging sensor does not matter, only the spectral band is important and the output interface of the electronic signal. Results were shown for the Basler acA1920 camera, which is used by many beam imaging systems.

Using such an approach, following the recommendations of the EMVA-1288 standard, would allow a fair comparison of different optical imaging systems for scintillator screens, ensuring that the quoted measurement parameters are understood to be the same.

Status and plans for beam instrumentation cameras at CERN

Enrico Bravin, CERN, Switzerland

An overview of the 200+ camera systems used at CERN for beam imaging was presented. These are still largely based on analogue cameras (CCTV type CCD, ThermoFisher CID, VIDICON) linked to a custom-made VME frame grabber. The advantages of analogue cameras over digital cameras were cited as being:

- Having a standardised readout, making them easy to replace with different brands
- Better suited for the radiation environment of particle accelerators
- Able to easily transport the signal over long distances

However, industry is rapidly moving away from such cameras, which will make it more and more difficult to find suitable replacements in the future. CERN is therefore investigating a move to digital cameras, which provide superior sensitivity, resolution and frame-rate, but need a dedicated infrastructure for signal transport and can suffer from hardware compatibility issues due to the non-standardisation of their readout. A comparison of analogue and digital camera sensors was presented, with the superior signal to noise ($\times 4$ - $\times 10$) of the digital cameras clearly demonstrated.

Another topic addressed was the use of intensifiers. These are commonly used to image weak sources or to allow gating on a fraction of the beam. Intensifiers were shown to suffer from life-time issues, with examples given of photo-cathode wear and MCP degradation.

In summary CERN is being forced to move away from CCTV and VIDICON cameras, with digital GigE cameras the preferred solution, provided mitigation measures can be found to allow their use in radiation areas.

Use of imaging fibre bundles as alternative to VIDICON tubes in high radiation areas

Damiano Celeste, CERN, Switzerland

The results of direct imaging using optical fibre bundles in radiation environments were presented. It was shown that using a fibre bundle the fraction of light collected is only 2% of that of a standard optical set-up. This in itself is not an issue, as the vastly superior sensitivity of the digital camera that can be used with the fibre bundle more than compensates, when compared to a radiation hard VIDICON camera. However, the images obtained were shown to be distorted due to fibre cross-talk or light leakage in the cladding, with the exact cause still under investigation.

Radiation tests carried out at the IRMA radiation facility in Saclay (France) showed that the fibre bundle (10m of Fujikura RadHard FIGR10 – 10,000 fibres of 1.5 mm diameter) was still giving an image after irradiation up to 700 kGy. However, the degradation due to radiation was found to be non-linear across the bundle, with the outer fibres having lost up to 70 % transmission while the central fibres had only lost 30%. This is suspected to come from the different mechanical stresses that the fibres experience during production, and is something that would need to be taken into account through regular calibration if such a system were to be used for profile measurements.

Radiation tests on cameras + tests of different screens in HiRadMat

Stephane Burger, CERN, Switzerland

The results of radiation tests carried out at the CHARM facility (CERN) on 6 different BASLER digital CMOS cameras were presented. Camera failures due to single event upsets were observed after a few minutes of exposure, requiring a power cycle to resume operation. The single event probability per shot (0.005 Gy, $5E7$ cm⁻² neutron equivalent fluence, $2E7$ cm⁻² high energy hadron fluence) was calculated to be 11%. The digital

cameras all failed irreversibly before accumulating 165 Gy. However, the response obtained from the last image before failure still had good contrast – much better than the image from an analogue camera exposed to the same radiation. Nevertheless, the analogue camera was still working after accumulating 500 Gy. The conclusion was that the sensor of the digital camera is unlikely to be the cause of the failure due to radiation, and that it is more likely to be the power supply, ADC or data transfer components. For many applications at CERN the 150 Gy limit for such a camera still makes it a viable alternative to analogue cameras, provided the probability of single event failure on a single shot remains at the % level.

Asked if the manufacturer could identify which component is failing, the answer was that there was little interest from the manufacturer to look into this for such a small market. A discussion was had on whether a specifically designed camera using one of the tested sensors could be pursued. This indeed seems like a possibility, but would require much better documentation from the sensor manufacturer, something which has been difficult to obtain up until now.

The presentation also covered the test of various screen materials at the CERN HiRadMat facility, where they were impacted by high energy density bunched beams. The tests were conducted in air, and therefore suffered from parasitic light from Cherenkov emission. Although some comparative light yield data from the various screens was presented, no precise light yield and resolution studies could be performed. There are now plans to repeat this test in a vacuum environment.

Session 4: Experiences at Proton and Ion Accelerators I (chair T. Lefevre)

Cameras at GSI / FAIR: Hardware – Software – Operation

Harald Bräuning, GSI, Germany

Driven by requests from the users, more and more scintillating screens have been upgraded to a digital readout in the last few years. The usage varies widely from continuous readout over many seconds with several frames per second to a single shot detection of μs long pulses triggered by machine events. Additional requirements were the simultaneous view of the images in the main control room and the experimental huts, storage of images for later analysis and measurement of beam position and approximate FWHM in SI units.

The new readout is also the prototype for scintillating screen readout in the FAIR accelerator complex, which is currently under construction. Integration into the new control system already implies a client-server architecture. The server part runs under Linux and is based on Cern's FrontEnd Software Architecture (FESA) with the client part written in Java/JavaFX. A priori, the number of clients per server is not restricted.

The standard assembly consists of a scintillating screen in a standardized holder mounted on a linear feedthrough normally driven by pressurized air. Calibration marks on the holder are used to determine the scale factors needed to convert pixel into meters. The screen is mounted under 45° with respect to the beam axis. In most, but not all, cases the camera is mounted under 90° with respect to the beam axis. The camera is equipped with a remote controlled lens. A LED is provided to illuminate the screen.

- For the camera, the UI-5240SE-M from iDS (<http://ids-imaging.com>) was chosen based on its e2v image sensor (EV76C560, <http://www.teledyne-e2v.com>). This sensor has a high sensitivity at a quantum efficiency of about 60% and a good radiation tolerance. Binning and an optional analogue gain boost of factor 2 further increase the sensitivity. In addition, the camera can be triggered by an external signal.
- Having a Gigabit Ethernet interface the cameras are read out by an industrial PC using a local network with a 10Gbit switch. The data acquisition software handles camera setting and image acquisition. Online processing includes cropping, rotation (90° , 180° and 270°), flipping and simple image scaling. Online analysis consists of creating projections in x and y as well as the intensity histogram. Centre-of-brightness and FWHM are calculated based on the projections without taking perspective distortions into account.
- An in-house built controller unit provides power for up to 8 cameras and the possibility to power-cycle a camera by remote command. It also distributes the trigger – initiated either by software command or by

the machine timing system – to the cameras. Currently there is only one trigger for all cameras connected to a controller unit.

- The purpose of the remote controlled lenses is to adjust the image brightness via the iris. Two types of lenses are used: Pentax -ER series and Linos MeVis-Cm. The Pentax lens has a manual focus and an iris control by a simple DC voltage. The iris closes automatically if the voltage is cut off. The Linos lens was intended as a replacement and features a motorized iris as well as focus. Using encoders for precise and reproducible adjustment it also requires a more complex controller. Both lenses are controlled with a PLC system with the PLC controller in the electronic rooms and satellites in a radiation safe area but close to the lenses. The PLC also controls the led for target illumination. Unfortunately, both lenses are now discontinued.
- Recently the readout of analogue cameras like the Thermo Fischer MegaRAD3 has been implemented using the Pleora iPort Analog-Pro external frame grabber. This module is Gigabit Ethernet based and compatible with the GigE Vision and GenICam standards. As analogue cameras have a fixed frame rate, a rate reduction in software to 10Hz reduces the amount of data transported from the server to the client. In addition, a software trigger is implemented by discarding all frames but the one directly following a machine event detected by the data acquisition software.
- The scintillating screen is typically mounted under 45° with respect to the optical axis. This together with the short distance between lens and screen leads to a visible perspective distortion where the scaling factor from pixels to meters is dependent on the position of the pixel itself. However, this position dependent scaling factor can be calculated based on 6 parameters obtained from the calibration marks on the standardized screen holder. While we do not rectify the image itself, these parameters are used by the client application to overlay a correct grid on top of the image, which shows the perspective correction. Using a movable cursor, the application will also calculate the correct position of the pixel under the cursor in meters.

Currently we have 34 iDS cameras in operation in environments dealing with all kinds of ions, energies and intensities. So far, the operation is stable and no degradation to radiation was observed. The cameras are well supported under Linux and integrate nicely with FESA. For short pulses (few μs length) it has been observed, that the image saturates with pixel values well below the maximum value of 255. However, further investigations have not yet been possible.

Three cameras with Pleora iPort Analog-Pro frame grabbers are currently in use. They are also well supported under Linux. Some stability problems have been observed with the frame grabber stopping to send images while still being accessible by the software. Currently we assume this to be network related although all frame grabbers are in a private network. But further investigations are necessary.

Scintillating Screen Performance Measurements for 300MeV/u Ion Beams at GSI

Beata Walasek-Höhne, GSI, Germany

This talk represents the investigations in the imaging properties of inorganic scintillation screens as diagnostic elements in heavy ion accelerator facilities, which were performed at the GSI Helmholtz Centre for Heavy Ion Research and the Technical University Darmstadt. The screen materials can be classified in groups of phosphor screens (P43 and P46 phosphor), single crystals (cerium-doped $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$) and poly-crystalline aluminium oxides (pure and chromium-doped Al_2O_3). Out of these groups, a selection of seven screens were irradiated by five different ion species (proton, nitrogen, nickel, xenon and uranium), that were extracted from SIS18 in fast (1 μs) and slow (300-400 ms) extraction mode at a specific energy of 300 MeV/u. The number of irradiating particles per pulse (ppp) was varied between 10^7 and $2 \cdot 10^{10}$ ppp and the scintillation response were recorded by a standard camera system.

Two detector systems were used simultaneously to obtain the response of the scintillating material to the irradiating beam. A standard camera system provided information on the light output L , the light yield Y and

the characteristics of the beam positions and profiles in horizontal and vertical direction. In parallel, a spectrometer recorded the spectral response of the materials.

Additionally, analytical methods like UV/VIS transmission spectroscopy, X-Ray diffraction and Raman fluorescence spectroscopy were used after the beam times to look for changes in the material structure. Neither structural variations nor material defects, induced by the ion irradiation, were proven within the accuracy range of the used instrumentation and the given ion fluencies.

Besides the irradiation under varying beam intensities, radiation hardness tests with fast and slow extracted Ni-ion beams at $2 \cdot 10^9$ ppp were performed to study the material stability under long time irradiation. The light yield Y of the targets was nearly constant or decreased only by about 10-15 % relative to the initial value. The emission spectra remained unchanged and the beam profiles showed good accordance to the reference methods.

During all performed experiments, the targets showed a great stability. Non-linear characteristics, e.g. due to quenching during irradiation at high beam intensities, were not observed. The light yield Y showed a tendency to decrease with increasing calculated electronic energy loss dE/dx . The characteristics of the calculated beam profiles as well as the recorded emission spectra did not change significantly. So a material degradation of the investigated materials was not verified. This observation is confirmed by the performed material characterization measurements. The need of target replacement, e.g. due to damage, did not occur and was thus not performed during the complete investigations.

Radiation hardness investigations of Al_2O_3 for MeV/u ions at GSI

Peter Forck, GSI, Germany

(Summary of PhD thesis by Stefan Lederer at Technical University Darmstadt 2016)

At the GSI heavy ion LINAC with energies up to 11.4 MeV/u several screen materials were investigated with the originally goal for a pepper-pot emittance measurement. A precise reproduction of the beamlet's size is fundamental for emittance calculation; in particular deformation by thermal effects and radiation damage at the beamlet's centre must be avoided. Results of those investigations for various scintillators were reported earlier; references are given in the talk. Thermal quenching has been investigated using screens equipped with an external heating system and has shown that the light yield decreases with increasing temperature as expected.

To investigate the radiation damage processes in detail, the un-doped scintillator Al_2O_3 in form a ceramic was investigated at GSI and HZDR with different ions in the energy range 0.5 to 5.9 MeV/u within a broad range of fluences up to some 10^{14} cm^{-2} . Al_2O_3 is an intrinsic scintillator, the luminescence is originated from different colour centres with maxima in the wavelength range of $\lambda = 322$ to 413 nm.

Even after radiation with a low fluence (e.g. 10^{12} cm^{-2}), the surface of the ceramic is discoloured at the beam spot; this shows the additional creation of colour centres. By annealing the original properties can be recovered. The light yield during irradiation decreases, but the rate depends significantly on the colour centre type. It was found that the F^+ centre (maximum at $\lambda = 326$ nm) is much more radiation hard than other centres. The decreasing light yield can be described by the so called Birks model which uses macroscopic quantities (cross section and quenching ratio) to describe the damage as a function of fluence. In particular, it was shown, that the light yield by radiation damage decreases initially, but level off to an almost constant level for large fluences. This is explained by an increasing probability that a projectile induced displaced atom is stopped in a corresponding location cancelling the damage effects, i.e. doesn't lead to a net-effect. The Birks model is applied to other ceramic scintillators irradiation showing the same general behaviour, but Al_2O_3 is most radiation hard, i.e. has lowest damage cross section and low quenching ratio.

The ion induced displacements at some MeV/u ions are not attributed to nuclear stopping. The damage is caused by the large electronic stopping power (basically close to the maximum of Bethe-Bloch equation), which heats the material around the ion track and leads to amorphisation and therefore for an increasing

density of colour centres. The so called thermal spike model is one possibility of describing such a process leading to the semi-empirical quantity of damage radius as a function of dose. For higher energetic ions the dose is lower, leading to less material heating around the ion track; this is confirmed by comparing the radiation damage as a function of fluence for ions in the range of MeV/u to the significantly lower damage of ions in the range of several 100 MeV/u.

Taking the radiation tolerance into account, the F⁺ centre emission (maximum at $\lambda = 326$ nm) could be used as for profile measurement by an appropriate optical filtering. Moreover, by moderate heating to e.g. 400 °C of the opaque ceramics with a backside heater, in-situ thermal annealing can be realized. This would enable precise profile and emittance measurements even for high beam currents.

Session 5: Experiences at Proton and ion Accelerators II (chair B. Walasek-Höhne)

Luminescence materials for high power targets

Cyrille Thomas, ESS, Lund, Sweden

Luminescent materials are used all over the world and in large range of application. One of them is to use luminescence properties for detecting high energy particles in high radiation environment such as high-power targets. This talk focuses on the example of imaging high power beam of particles, typically of the order of 1MW average beam power or higher, delivered to a target that can be used for instance for neutron spallation. The imaging application is highly challenging by many aspects. First of all, the requirements on the materials are strong: the luminescence yield is expected to be high, in the range of 100 thousand photons per MeV, constant and linear; it is expected to be independent from temperature variation; the fluorescence lifetime has to be less than 1 μ s for capturing fast events; the material lifetime has to be long enough to support operation of the accelerator.

The case beam on target imaging system for the 5 MW beam at the European Spallation Source ERIC is presented in this talk. It introduces the imaging system and the imposed performance on the material. The talk presents the selected material which is similar to the material used at various facilities like for instance the CERN LHC Dump imaging system or the SNS beam on target imaging system. The properties of this material is discussed and it is shown, that in spite of not quite matching all the required performance, this material will be used for the first target and probably the next one. We also focus on the degradation aspect of the material. Irradiation studies have been carried out on this material and some of the early results are shown.

Screens from the SNS-Target

W. Blokland, SNS, Oak Ridge, USA

The spallation Neutron Source uses a Al₂O₃:Cr coating on the target nose cone to see where the beam hits the target. The coating composition and spraying technique has been developed in collaboration with Stony Brook. After installation and exposure to proton beam, the coating has been tested or evaluated for: spectral response, comparison with calculated beam parameters, uniformity tests, decay in Luminescence per MWhr, effect of DPA on profile, effect of DPA on spectrum, linearity of luminescence vs beam pulse charge, duration of luminescence pulse, and calculated effect of secondary particles on luminescence. Various results are shown in Figure 1. The main issue is the loss of luminescence due to the radiation damage.

Figure 1: Various measurements performed on the SNS target coating.

The decay in luminescence per MWhr was measured but the curve was not understood. However, the Empirical Birks model (1) was given in P. Forck’s talk “Radiation hardness investigations of Al₂O₃ for MeV/u ions at GSI”, and this model turned out to be a good, not perfect, fit of the measured decay as shown in Figure 2. This model and other mechanisms presented at the workshop should help our understanding of the radiation damage effects.

$$S(\Phi) = S(0) \cdot \frac{1}{1+K \cdot [1-\exp(-\sigma_D \Phi)]} \quad (1)$$

with $K = \frac{k_q}{k_f + k_i}$: effect on emission as ratio between, k_q : quenching by damage i.e. displacement, k_i : internal quenching, k_f : regular luminescence emission.

Figure 2: Fit of Birks model to the SNS Luminescence versus MWHrs of proton beam exposure.

While the current luminescent coating works for SNS, we are searching for a longer lasting brightness of the coating and will continue looking into the radiation effects and testing different coatings on our target.

Overview for RHIC complex: Screens for electrons, protons and ions

T. Miller, BNL, Brookhaven, USA

The RHIC complex of accelerators at Brookhaven National Laboratory maintains a group of five ion machines in support of nuclear research by ion collision as well as three electron machines for

cooling and lensing of the ion beams. Imaging of low intensity ion beams has employed principally doped ceramic screens as well as some scintillating screens; whereas the electron machines mostly rely on monocrystalline YAG screens with some experimental nanotube screens. This presentation provides an overview of these machines and the types of screens used. Details such as optical configuration, camera systems, control topology and failure history are also covered.

Usage of scintillation screens at the medical facility HIT

H. Latzel, HIT, Heidelberg, Germany

The Heidelberg Ion Beam Therapy Center (HIT) is a medical radiation facility where cancer patients are treated with carbon ions and protons by means of a scanned pencil beams. To ensure clinically acceptable treatment conditions the position and the width of the individual pencil beams must be monitored with a precision of less than 1 mm in position deviation and $\pm 10\%$ in width. One of the three treatment rooms is the heavy ion gantry to rotate the ion beam around the patient thus using optimal beam angles. Because of the axial symmetry at the gantry it seems obvious to make use of an ion beam detector with similar symmetry. One possible implementation of such a detector is the construction of a scintillation screen in conical shape. For this reason, we have set up a prototype of a conical scintillation screen to demonstrate the feasibility of this technique to measure beam position and spot size at the iso-centre within sufficient accuracy.

First results from measurements at a horizontal beam line treatment room and at the gantry show that position measurements are accurate to 0.1 mm. The reconstruction of correct beam spot sizes in the iso-centric plane from the scintillating light on the curved inner surface of the conical screen is more difficult. For all proton beam energies and low and mid-energies of the carbon beams, the results correspond to the expected spot size. At higher carbon beam energies, the divergence from the expected values are bigger, thus the mathematical model still needs to be improved. The next version of the conical scintillation screen includes further optimizations of the camera, optics, and mechanical setup.

Session 6: Experiences at Electron Accelerators I (chair G. Kube)

Experiences with different screen material at ALBA

Ubaldo Iriso, ALBA-CELLS, Cerdanyola del Vallés, Spain

At ALBA scintillating screens are used for three different types of monitors: in conventional screen monitors where the scintillator screen interacts directly with the electron beam, as X-ray converter in In-Air X-ray detectors (IXD), and as X-ray converter for pinhole cameras. All types of monitors were covered in this contribution. Standard screen monitors for the ALBA transfer lines, linac, booster and storage ring were equipped with YAG:Ce scintillators (0.5 mm thickness, supplier Crytur), some of them additionally with OTR screens; observation geometry is 45° screen tilt angle with optics perpendicular to the beam axis. Comparative studies between OTR and YAG screen profile measurements indicated that the scintillator based beam profiles are systematically enlarged (U. Iriso et al., Proc. DIPAC'09) which was attributed to the scintillating screen thickness. Therefore, linac screens were exchanged from 0.5 mm to 0.1 mm thickness, now emittance measurements agree well with OTR measurements for bunch charges typically smaller than 2 nC. Concerning IXD monitors, LYSO:Ce screens from two different suppliers were investigated (PreLude 420, Saint Gobain and CRY-19, Crytur), and it was found that the latter one had an about 30% higher light yield for 1 mm screen thickness. However, the IXD based vertical beam profiles are systematically enlarged compared to pinhole measurements which is not yet understood. For the ALBA pinhole camera measurement the observation geometry is such that the YAG:Ce scintillator (0.1 mm/0.2 mm thickness) surface normal is

collinear to the X-ray beam axis with the optics being perpendicular to this axis. In view of accurate beam emittance measurements for the main storage ring the question was raised how precise absolute beam sizes could be determined: while good agreement was found for relative beam size evolution, pinhole based measurements at ALBA showed small differences compared to LOCO based calculations. It was shown that image analysis and acquisition parameters play an important role when looking at micrometer precision level. As consequence a “feedback” system will be implemented at ALBA to keep similar CCD illumination conditions.

- **Jefferson Lab Scintillating Screens**

Kevin Jordan, Jefferson Lab, Newport News (VA), USA

A brief overview was given of the JLab accelerators, consisting of CEBAF (Continuous Electron Beam Accelerator Facility), LERF (Low Energy Recirculation Facility, former FEL), UITS (Ultimate Injector Test Facility), and GTS (Gun Test Stand). While the latter two facilities operate with YAG:Ce screens, CEBAF is equipped with 139 Chromox screens and 6 YAG screens. Due to the high failure rate of Vidicon and CCD cameras mounted close to the screens, an upgraded optics setup was designed to bring the cameras away from these radiation sources. At GTS, YAG screen damage could be observed: under UV light exposure bleaching damage became visible. The application of powder phosphor coated screens was described, having the advantage that any geometry can be spray coated using phosphor spraying techniques. As an example the FEL beam dump screen was presented. With boron nitride nano tubes (BNNT) a new scintillator material was presented, having the advantage that it is very radiation resistant and suitable for high power beam applications. Experiments with this new material were performed for beam energies from 300 keV up to 11 GeV and first results presented.

- **Screen Monitors in SwissFEL**

Rasmus Ischebeck, Paul Scherrer Institut, Villigen, Switzerland

Design and operation of the SwissFEL screen monitors were presented. The SwissFEL with beam energies from 5 MeV up to 6 GeV is equipped with 27 transverse profile imagers which are routinely in operation since 2016. Before finalizing the design, different cameras, scintillators (main material: YAG:Ce, supplier Crytur) and imaging geometries were tested. Design goals were operation at bunch charges between 10 and 200 pC, 10 μm resolution, 100 Hz readout, and immunity to COTR effects. The screen monitor imaging geometry is based on a geometrical optimization, described in detail in Ref. (R. Ischebeck et al., PRST-AB 18 082802), the cameras are operated in Scheimpflug geometry. Different measurement examples demonstrated the high quality which is achievable with this kind of screen monitor, as for example transverse emittance measurements and investigations of the longitudinal phase space in combination with a transverse deflecting cavity. Further applications of scintillator based beam monitors were briefly described, as the beam loss monitor system and X-ray profile monitors.

Experiences with scintillators screen at FERMI

Marco Veronese, Elettra-Sincrotrone Trieste, Italy

The 1.5 GeV seeded FERMI FEL at Elettra is equipped with about 40 screen monitors, starting from the gun up to the main beam dump. They typically consist of a combination of YAG:Ce and OTR screens. From the first bunch compressor onward, FERMI is suffering from COTR effects, therefore only scintillating screens are used in order to suppress this influence. For the intra-undulator screens a re-design was performed in order to achieve a COTR immune geometry. The achieved resolution amounted to $< 15 \mu\text{m}$ with a YAG screen thickness of 100 μm . Different applications of intra-undulator type screen monitors were presented, for example (i) the measurement of the seed laser to electron beam trajectory overlap, (ii) the seed laser pointing stability, and (iii) the imaging of the FEL radiation. For seed laser applications ($\lambda = 260 \text{ nm}$) it was

demonstrated that UV scintillators (Metrolux K6) are better suited than YAG screens, for the FEL radiation measurements damage of the coating material onto YAG screens was observed. In order to be more confident, presently a new hybrid screen/wire scanner diagnostics is under commissioning. In the future, three additional screen monitor upgrades are planned, aiming mainly to increase the achievable resolution.

- **Session 7: Experiences at Electron Accelerators II (chair A.Wawrzyniak)**

Scintillation screens for laser-accelerated beams

Jurjen P. Couperus Cabadař, Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden – Rossendorf, Germany

Scintillating screens are routinely used as beam diagnostic for electrons and proton beams originating from high-intensity short-pulse laser based novel accelerators.

In laser wakefield accelerators (LWFA), powdered rare earth phosphor ($Gd_2O_2S:Tb$) based scintillating screens are typically applied in dipole dispersive spectrometers in order to retrieve the accelerator's electron energy distribution over a large spectral range^{1,2}. The charge to photon response is calibrated for several commercially available screens. This allows them to be used for absolute charge measurements of electron beams³. A method for error-avoiding cross-laboratory implementation of these calibrations is presented. Additionally, saturation, degeneration and damage effects in long-term usage of such screens are considered.

For laser-driven ion sources (LDIS), common detection methods such as radiochromic films (RCF) and solid state track detectors (e.g., CR39) offer two-dimensional detection of the transverse angularly resolved spectrum, however do not allow for online readout. Here, two alternative scintillator based detectors offering online detection are presented. A 1D stack detector offers a high spatial resolution and energy resolution⁴. A 2D pixelated stack detector with varying absorber thicknesses gives a slightly lower spatial resolution, but offers a full two-dimensional spatial measurement of both the beam profile and energy distribution⁵.

¹ J.P. Couperus *et al.*, Nat. Commun. **8**, 487 (2017)

² A. Irman *et al.*, Plasma Phys. Control. Fusion **60**, 044015 (2018)

³ T. Kurz *et al.*, Rev. Sci. Instrum. **89**, 093303 (2018)

⁴ J. Metzkes *et al.*, Rev. Sci. Instrum. **83**, 123301 (2012)

⁵ J. Metzkes *et al.*, Rev. Sci. Instrum. **87**, 083310 (2016)

Performance of a Reflective Microscope Objective and Thin Scintillator in an X-ray Pinhole Camera

Lorraine Bobb, Diamond Light Source, UK

At synchrotron light sources, X-ray pinhole cameras are commonly used to measure the transverse profile of the electron beam in the storage ring. From these profile measurements and given knowledge of the accelerator lattice, the beam emittance is calculated.

As improvements to the accelerator lattice reduce the beam emittance, e.g. with upgrades to fourth generation synchrotron light sources, likewise the beam size will be reduced such that micron and sub-micron scale resolution is required for beam size measurement. Therefore, the spatial resolution (i.e. point spread function) of the X-ray pinhole camera must be improved accordingly.

In the literature it is well documented that the scintillator screen significantly contributes to the overall point spread function of the X-ray pinhole camera. To reduce this contribution, a thin scintillator screen may be used. However, a thin screen will also produce a lower photon yield.

This presentation discusses the importance of matching the scintillator screen thickness to the numerical aperture of the relay lens. For optimal spatial resolution, the performance of a thin (25 μ m) LuAg:Ce screen combined with a reflective microscope objective is compared to the nominal setup consisting of a thick (200 μ m) LuAg:Ce screen and a high quality refractive lens. The observed degradation of Prelude420 (LYSO) and LuAG:Ce screens from exposure to the X-ray beam is also presented.

Towards a bunch-resolved transverse beam-profile monitor for BESSY II and BESSY VSR

Gregor Schiwietz, Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin, Berlin, Germany

After an introduction of the ongoing BESSY VSR project (Variable pulse-length Storage Ring) in Berlin with new hardware installations and resulting timing pattern, the corresponding requirements for beam diagnostics are discussed. These requirements lead to three new beamlines for optical and THz diagnostics at two dipole magnets. The first new diagnostic beamline is in operation since January 2019. It allows for streak-camera measurements, but also for direct beam imaging of larger profiles as well as interferometry of the vertical size by using the X-Ray baffle method.

Double-slit interferometry using visible light has already been proven at BESSY and will be installed permanently at the second diagnostic beamline. The principle for accurate horizontal as well as vertical beam-size determination with this method is presented in detail. Results are shown in comparison to existing pinhole monitors. Planned and ongoing improvements of the sensitivity of the setup are explained as well the coupling to a fast intensified CCD (ICCD) that will enable bunch-resolved interferometry for transverse beam-profiling.

Collaboration Study of Coherent Optical Transition Radiation Effects on Profile Screen Measurements

Patrick Krejcik, SLAC, Rasmus Ischebeck, PSI, Changbum Kim, PAL

Linac based FELs produce ultra-short bunches with low longitudinal emittance (energy spread). The high peak current (kiloAmps) and microbunching instability conspire to generate Coherent Optical Transition Radiation COTR at the surface of all profile monitor screen materials. The OTR becomes coherent when the microbunch length is comparable to the radiation wavelength. The COTR is both unstable and many orders of magnitude brighter, making screens unusable. We present screen designs that mitigate this effect by directing the COTR away from the camera while preserving the optical resolution from the YAG screen using a geometry that accounts for the refraction Snell angle in the screen and the tilted Scheimpflug angle in the image plane to preserve depth of field. The influence of coherent diffraction radiation is also minimized in the latest design by arranging the internal vacuum mirrors to be further away from the beam axis. Results are presented showing the success of the design by scanning the bunch length at the LCLS beam line in the range from 1 to 10 kA peak current.

- **Session 8: Experiences at Electron Accelerators III (chair U. Iriso)**

Screen Charging Effects at the European XFEL

A. Novokshono, DESY, Hamburg, Germany

The beam passing through the off-axis screen monitors causes an ionization inside the scintillator, which in this case is either LYSO or YAP with 200um thickness. The scintillator then slowly discharges, which in turn induces a Coulomb force that affects the passing of subsequent bunches and so, it affects the beam orbit and the SASE level.

Artem showed us several studies done to characterize this effect. From simulations with GEANT4, they concluded that the scintillator charge could be up to 3% of the bunch charge. On the other hand, experimental beam studies evaluated this effect into 6% of the bunch charge.

It is suspected that this disagreement might be related with a faster scintillator discharge as the expected. For this reason, further systematic studies are planned at XFEL to characterize this effect. As a possible solution, it was discussed to cover the scintillator by a conductive layer to discharge it as fast as possible.

Observation of Quenching Effects in Scintillators at the European XFEL

Gero Kube, DESY, Hamburg, Germany

The beam shape at the screen monitors at the European XFEL presented a weird “smoke-ring” shape, which resulted in a measured emittance values larger than expected. This shape was not consistent with COTR contribution or CCD saturation, and they started to look at possible causes.

Gero carefully explained the scintillation process, and modelled the electron passage inside the screen as a “straight tube” of ionization with Fermi Radius $R_F = hc/h\omega_p$. High primary (electron) beam densities results in a “quenching” of the excitation carriers, consistent with the appearance of the observed smoke-rings type shapes. For LYSO scintillators, the high density thresholds were in the order of 1nC beams into $\sigma \sim 100\mu\text{m}$.

Currently, they are also testing different screens to reduce this effect both theoretically and experimentally. Theoretically, the quest is focused on Gadolinium-based scintillators (where charge carriers rapidly transfer their energy to the excited state of Gadolinium), or YAP (where high mobility of excitation carriers reduce the quenching probability). So far, first tests with YAP and YAG showed better results than with LYSO.

Characterization of the spatial frequency response of a scintillator for beam size measurements using Heterodyne Near Field Speckles

M. Siano, University of Milano, Italy

A novel interferometric technique has been tested at the NCD-SWEET beamline at ALBA for two-dimensional beam size measurements. It relies on Fourier analysis of X-ray speckles formed by interfering the incoming radiation from an undulator with a number of spherical waves scattered by nanoparticles suspended in water.

To this aim, the spatial frequency response of the system (particle form factor and dynamics + YAG screen + relay optics) plays a fundamental role. Its effects are accounted for by introducing the Instrumental Transfer Function (ITF) in the model. It is shown how it can be characterized with the same technique and experimental setup.

Mirko shows and discusses recent results at ALBA. The measured horizontal beam size ($\sigma_h = 115 \mu\text{m}$) is in good agreement with expectations (130 μm), while the vertical one ($\sigma_v = 16 \mu\text{m}$) is a factor of two larger (7 μm). This discrepancy is still under study.

He finally focuses on the measured ITF. While the sample contributions can be neglected, effects of defocusing of the microscope objective with respect to the YAG screen are evidenced. Nonetheless, the ITF is well described by an exponential decay, which might be primarily dictated by the YAG. Further tests and simulations are needed to confirm this.

- ARIES-ADA Topical Workshop
- Experiences during Hadron LINAC Commissioning
- Online Workshop, January 25th to 29th, 2021
- INDICO-site: <https://agenda.ciemat.es/event/1229/>
- Workshop Summary

Editors: A. Alexandrov - SNS, W. Blokland - SNS, P. Forck - GSI, O. Kester – TRIUMF, J. Marroncle - CEA/Saclay, C. Oliver – CIEMAT, I. Podadera – CIEMAT, A. Reiter – GSI, F. Roncarolo – CERN, V. Scarpine - FNAL, Liu Yong – KEK

- Organised and sponsored by:

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- **Workshop introduction and goals (Peter Forck - GSI, Ivan Podadera - CIEMAT)**

- Within the frame of ARIES-ADA, topical workshops are executed to discuss actual subjects not covered in such a detailed manner at typical conferences but which are relevant for ongoing developments. Recent achievements during hadron LINAC commissioning and operation were reported at this workshop, and the international participants summarised long-term experiences.

- The aims of this workshop on ‘Experiences during Hadron LINAC Commissioning’ were to:
 - Bring together instrument designers, experts, and research groups working on proton or ion linear accelerators' commissioning.
 - Review the experiences on the commissioning of hadron LINACs from the first day of operation to more regular operation.
 - Discuss the discrepancies between the beam instruments requirements specified at the design phase and the real needs and applications requirements during commissioning.
 - Explore the feedback about the LINAC layout and usage of diagnostics test benches during stage-based commissioning.
 - Strengthen existing collaborations between groups and develop new ones. LIPAC is a superconducting

Originally, the workshop was planned as a face-to-face meeting to be hosted in Segovia (Spain) in June 2020. However, due to the Corona pandemic it was cancelled and then executed as a remote workshop from January 25th to 29th, 2021 from 14:00 to about 17:30 o'clock Central European Time. The workshop comprises 30 oral presentations in life-format from laboratories in America (7 contributions), Asia (5 contributions) and Europe (18 contributions) as well as 10 discussion sessions of 10 to 35 minutes' duration. The program and presentations are available on <https://agenda.ciemat.es/event/1229>. The talks were not pre-recorded and are accompanied by short discussion to keep the workshop atmosphere. The remote format has the advantage that more people can participate; for this workshop 239 people registered from America, Asia and Europe with a distribution of 9 %, 21 % and 70 %, respectively. In average more than 100 people were connected simultaneously and participate in a lively manner to the discussion, see figure below.

The workshop was jointly organised by CIEMAT and GSI with Dr. Ivan Podadera and Dr. Peter Forck as the chairpersons. The program committee consists of: Alexander Aleksandrov – SNS, Peter Forck – GSI, Jacques Marroncle - CEA-Saclay, Ivan Podadera – CIEMAT, Federico Roncarolo – CERN, Victor Scarpine – FNAL, supported for technical issues by Diego Obradors – CIEMAT. In addition to the program committee members, sessions were chaired by Willem Blokland - SNS, Oliver Kester - TRIUMF, Conception Oliver - CIEMAT, Andreas Reiter - GSI, Liu Yong – KEK.

The number of online workshop participants as a function of daytime.

- **Session 1: Superconducting CW LINAC I (chair: Ivan Podadera - CIEMAT)**
- **Commissioning of test bench at LIPAc accelerator**

David Jimenez-Rey, CIEMAT, Madrid, Spain

The LIPAC is a superconducting CW 1 MW deuteron accelerator, prototype of the IFMIF accelerator, being now commissioned in Rokkasho (Japan). The accelerator is being constructed as a collaboration between Europe and Japan with the aim of validating the technology to build a fusion-like 5 MW neutron source (IFMIF).

LIPAC is commissioned in four stages. Phase A is the commissioning of the Injector up to CW and was already finished in 2017. Phase B is the one of RFQ and MEBT at low duty cycle (1 ms / 1 Hz) and ended up in 2019. Phase B+, which is now ongoing, is the commissioning of RFQ and MEBT at CW with a High Power Beam Dump. Phase C and D are both the commissioning of the superconducting LINAC, at low and high duty cycle respectively. During Phase B, a 125 mA deuteron beam was accelerated up to 5 MeV and transported along the MEBT, with a pulse length of 1 ms at 1 Hz.

Sixteen weeks were scheduled for Phase B, between July 2018 and July 2019. The commissioning started with a low current proton beam at a low duty cycle and was later increased in current up to similar space-charge conditions as of the nominal deuteron beam, before switching to the deuteron beam.

During this Phase, first step was optimisation of the beam current (transmission), with target at the Low Power Beam Dump measurement. Voltage scan of the RFQ were done to optimise the transmission. Current transformers were the key devices at this stage. Later, transverse profiles were measured using SEM grids, and information correlated (at low currents) with residual gas fluorescence profile monitors. Beam position was also checked, and the energy calculated from the BPM's. Transverse emittance was also calculated using slit/steerer/SEM grid combination, with very good agreement with the simulated one. Beam losses were measured with ionisation chambers Beam Loss Monitors during deuteron operation. Scintillator and neutron detectors were used before during proton operation.

Some of the problems found in the instruments were: 1) offset problems with the ACCT, 2) absolute calibration of the BPM's, especially for the energy measurements, 3) damage of the wires due to pressure waves during venting of the accelerator, 4) radiation background for fluorescence profile monitors operation, 5) lack of signal of ionisation chambers during proton operation, 6) EMC and ground problems of some equipment.

Phase B+ is planned to start during the first half of 2021. Finally, for the commissioning of the superconducting LINAC (Phases C/D), CVD diamond detectors for micro-loss monitoring and beam position monitors will be installed inside the cryomodule for operation. The diagnostics plate will be placed downstream the cryomodule for characterisation of the 9 MeV CW beam.

Commissioning of normal and superconducting LINACs at GSI

Winfried Barth, GSI Darmstadt and University Mainz, Germany

GSI accelerator facility and Linac injector strategy: An UNILAC upgrade program is designated to prepare for high intensity high current heavy-ion, as well as for proton synchrotron injector operation for the Facility of Antiproton and Ion Research (FAIR). As a result, high duty factor beam time availability for the research

program at GSI UNILAC will be strongly diminished due to the duty factor limitation for FAIR injector operation.

High Current Injector commissioning: The disassembly of the Unilac pre-stripper linac (linac for all ions, final energy 1.4 MeV/u) of the Wideröe type took place in 1999. An increase of more than two orders of magnitude in particle number for the heaviest elements in the SIS had to be gained. Since that time the new High Current Injector (HSI) consisting was installed and successfully commissioned. The High Charge Injector (HLI) supplied the main linac during that time. Simultaneously conditioning and running in of the RF-transmitters and RF-structures were performed. The HSI commissioning strategy included beam investigation after each transport and acceleration section, using a versatile diagnostic test stand. Extensive commissioning measurements (e.g. transverse emittance, bunch width, beam transmission) behind LEPT, RFQ, Super Lens, IH tank I and II and stripping section had been accomplished. An $^{40}\text{Ar}^{1+}$ beam delivered by a MUCIS ion source was used to fill the linac up to the theoretical space charge limit. Routine operation started in November 1999. Serious degradation effects at the electrode surface of the 10m long HSI-RFQ required the repeated exchange of RFQ-rods – further improvements of RFQ-performance could be accomplished with a temporarily installed versatile beam diagnostics test bench.

11.4 MeV/u charge separator commissioning: A charge state separator system was installed in the transfer line to the SIS 18. After commissioning all components, beam commissioning was performed successfully with a heavy ion beam; the measured beam transmission was close to 100 % for low and high current beams. The improved charge separation capability was simulated beforehand. Simulated and measured emittance growth effects are caused by small-angle straggling; additionally, the charge separator's vertical emittance is increased by dispersion. With an advanced beam diagnostics bench, integrated into the beamline, measurements are accomplished to prepare for the injection into the SIS 18. Besides ion current, the beam profile and position, the emittance, the beam energy, and the bunch structure could be measured.

Superconducting heavy-ion cw-Linac (HEmholtz Linear ACcelerator): Nine superconducting CH cavities operated at 217 MHz provide ion acceleration to beam energies between 3.5 MeV/u and 7.3 MeV/u, while the energy spread should be kept smaller than ± 3 keV/u. A conceptual layout of the HELIAC was worked out, allowing the acceleration of highly charged ions with a mass to charge ratio of up to 6. For proper beam focusing superconducting solenoids have to be mounted between the CH cavities. The R&D demonstrator setup, embedded in a newly upgraded radiation protection cave, is located in the straightforward direction of the HLI. The vendor Research Instruments GmbH (RI) provided for sufficient cavity preparation. After high pressure rinsing (HPR) and advanced performance testing the initial design quality factor Q_0 has been exceeded by a factor of four, a maximum accelerating gradient of $E_{\text{acc}} = 9.6$ MV/m at $Q_0 = 8.14 \cdot 10^8$ has been achieved. Prior to beam commissioning, the RF power coupler was tested and conditioned with a dedicated test resonator. At June 28th, 2017, after successful set up of the matching line and short commissioning and ramp up time of some days, the CH-cavity accelerated heavy ion beams (Ar^{11+}) with full transmission first time up to the design beam energy of 1.866 MeV/u. The bunch length measured with the bunch shape monitor (BSM) was measured as very sensitive to RF-phase changes. A change of RF-phase by 30° only, leads to a change of bunch length by more than a factor of 4, while the beam transmission is not affected.

Beam Commissioning at FRIB

Tomofumi Maruta, FRIB Michigan State University, East Lansing, USA

The FRIB Injector LINAC accelerates all stable ion species to more than 200 MeV/u using 300 superconducting RF resonators, providing 400 kW to the production target. The accelerator is divided into the following sections: a front-end (ion source, LEPT, RFQ and MEPT), a 3 LINAC segment (LS1, LS2 and LS3), two folding

segments (FS1 and FS2) and a Beam Delivery System to the target. The duty cycle is flexible: CW or pulsed. The design allows simultaneous multi-charge state beam acceleration (e.g. 33+ and 34+ of ^{238}U). Two objectives were defined for completing the beam commissioning: acceleration of ^{36}Ar with energy >200 MeV/u and current > 20 pA, and acceleration of ^{86}Kr to produce ^{84}Se by fragmentation.

The commissioning was split into six phases: 1) Front-end (Ion Source, LEBT, RFQ, MEBT), 2) cryomodels $\beta=0.041$ of LS1, 3) rest of LS1 and first dipole of FS1, 4) rest of FS1, LS2, part of FS2 to the straight dump, 5) rest of FS2, LS3, BDS, 6) target. The commissioning started in May 2017, and Phase 4 was completed by 2020.

During front-end commissioning, a complete set of diagnostics was available along the line for beam tuning and finding set points of optical devices: Allison scanner, pepper pot, image viewers, wire profile monitors, BPM's, faraday cups, current monitors, 4-jaw slits, choppers and attenuators.

Before Phase 1, beam optics was simulated (FLAME, TRACK and IMPACT) for ^{40}Ar and expected measurements at diagnostics, which later agreed to all with the experiments. ^{40}Ar and ^{86}Kr beam were successfully accelerated to 0.5 MeV/u by RFQ, as confirmed by a dipole magnet in MEBT, with a transmission of 85%.

During Phase 2, the beam was for the first time transported through superconducting RF resonators. Argon accelerated up to 2 MeV/u by twelve QWR ($\beta=0.041$) in three cryomodels. A diagnostics plate was installed after the cryomodels with the following measurements: absolute energy measurement by Silicon detector, beam profile measurements in transverse and longitudinal, current and position measurements. A phase scan application worked well. The energy was calculated by TOF of two BPM's, only 0.2 eμA are necessary to measure a bunch arrival with respect to the reference RF. The scans are made at 20% of design amplitude to determine the arrival phase and then increase energy up to the nominal one.

In Phase 3, the complete LS1 was commissioned in February 2019, with four ion species (^{40}Ar , ^{86}Kr , ^{20}Ne and ^{129}Xe) accelerated up to 20 MeV/u. Charge stripping with the carbon foil was demonstrated, to be used for first operation (liquid lithium stripper for high power operation will be installed as an alternative). Transverse and longitudinal emittance after LS1 were measured, without evidence of emittance growth in the transverse plane. Around 300 W were transported without any beam loss (CW operation, or high current at low duty). Faulty studies with cavity and cryomodels off were studied, achieving full transmission with small loss detection ($5 \cdot 10^{-4}$).

The capacity of accelerating a two charge-state beam for ^{86}Kr along the sc linac was also demonstrated. However, while there is full transmission at the end of the linac, a trajectory displacement of up to 7 mm was found. Reason for this displacement was the misalignment of front-end elements. Although all elements were aligned with 0.2 mm in 2017, the installation of the LS1 cryomodels deformed the floor, which cause the optical elements to increase the misalignment to ± 0.5 mm.

During 2020, LS2 was commissioned and the main functions verified, ^{36}Ar was accelerated up to 204 MeV/u and ^{129}Xe and ^{86}Kr up to more than 180 MeV/u. Multi-charge state acceleration was demonstrated as well, with e.g. three charge states of ^{129}Xe (49+, 50+ and 51+) simultaneously accelerated. The measured transverse and longitudinal beam positions are close to the design. High level applications were developed for beam study, and tests of ion species change in a short time were performed successfully.

- [Session 2: Superconducting CW LINAC II \(chair Jacques Marroncle - CEA/Saclay\)](#)

- **SARAF Phase I: Commissioning and operation experiences**

Leo Weissmann, Soreq NRC SARAF, Yavne, Israel

The history of Phase I of the SARAF project was described listing some of the issues that the SARAF group faced over the period lasted more than 15 years. Firstly, the development of a novel fast chopper technique was highlighted. Secondly, the broad range of activities devoted to bringing the SARAF RFQ to the Phase II specifications were described. This included the major modifications such as the addition of the second coupler, and design, machining, and commissioning of the new rods structure. It was then the turn of the Prototype Super conducting Module (PSM), which was submitted to repairs: replacement of piezo-tuners, development of the in-house RF amplifiers, DC biasing the RF couplers allowing one achieving a stable 2 mA CW proton beam. The problems in the operation of PSM at high-current CW beam were emphasised. Postmortem analysis of the PSM cavities may give one new insight with this regard.

The learned lessons were implemented into the design of the Phase II cryomodules. Some challenges in the transport of intense beams through the beam lines were encountered, including an accident in which a hole was drilled by the beam in a magnet's chamber. Finally, some time was spent describing the first prototype of a liquid lithium jet target (LiLIT 1), evoking briefly LiLIT 2 which was commissioned in 2018, and a liquid Gallium target, which is being constructed for use as a Phase II beam dump. The operation statistics and the scientific output of Phase I was presented, and the progress in Phase II construction was outlined. In conclusion, the presenter emphasised the importance of Phase I of SARAF for the Israeli nuclear physics community and expressed hope that the experience, accumulated by the SARAF team, would help in the successful implementation of Phase II project.

Commission of Spiral2

Christophe Jamet, GANIL, Caen, France

A global view of the commissioning of SPIRAL2 with a beam diagnostic feedback is presented.

The SPIRAL2 accelerator, built on the GANIL's facility, at CAEN in FRANCE is dedicated to accelerate light and heavy ion beams up to 5mA and 40 MeV. The continuous wave accelerator is based on two ECR ion sources, a RFQ and a superconducting LINAC.

The beam commissioning is planned in 4 phases, qualification of the ion sources and LEPT in laboratories, qualification of the injector on a Diagnostic Plate, LINAC beam commissioning and first experiment to NFS and S3 experimental halls.

MEBT results give a good beam transport agreement between simulation and measurement and an RFQ transmission near 100% with H⁺, ⁴He²⁺ and ¹⁸O⁶⁺ beams. The commissioning shows that emittance-meter in the MEBT is essential. The commissioning time associated with the D-plate was well invested. The design of the D-Plate and compatibility between diagnostics have to be well analysed before.

The LINAC tuning is performed in several steps, beam alignments, amplitude and Phase tunings of cavities by a signature matching method, a matching of the MEBT beam to the LINAC channel and finally a slow increase of the power.

In November 2019, a first proton beam was accelerated at the nominal energy, 33 MeV.

The objective of 2020 was obtained in November with a proton beam of 16 kW, one tenth of the final value at full power. SPIRAL2 is a challenge for diagnostic monitors in term of intensity dynamic range. All beam diagnostics meet the design specifications but not yet the physics requirements in term of intensity (down to 100 nA for physic experiments). All beam diagnostics meet the design specifications even if optimisations and modifications continue.

The main objective for the accelerator, in 2021, is to become a stable neutron facility for the experimental room NFS.

Beam Commissioning of PIP-II Injector Test (PIP2IT) H⁻ LINAC

Alexander Shemyakin, Fermilab, Batavia, USA

The PIP2IT test accelerator models the low-energy part of the future PIP-II H⁻ LINAC at Fermilab. In its present configuration, the PIP2IT consists of the 30 keV H⁻ ion source, LEBT, 2.1 MeV RFQ, long MEBT with a bunch-by-bunch chopper, and two cryomodules operating in CW: Half-Wave Resonator (162.5 MHz) and Single-Spoke Resonator -1 (325 MHz).

The warm front end was fully commissioned in 2018 with complete characterisation of the beamline optics and beam parameters.

Installation of all major components was finished in December 2020. Commissioning so far has been focused mostly on the acceleration of a short-pulse beam. In the 2 mA x 10 μ s x 20 Hz regime, the beam energy was measured using the BPM system at 17 MeV with accuracy better than 1%.

The scatter in BPM readings was analysed to distinguish the component related to the beam jitter. This component is likely to be defined by the noise in the ion source HV power supply. The remaining noise corresponds to 0.01 mm rms in transverse positions and 0.1 $^{\circ}$ rms in Phase.

The PIP2IT program will end in Spring'2021. By that time, it is expected that

- the MEBT chopper is commissioned, and 0.55 ms pulses with an aperiodic bunch structure are accelerated to full energy
- all available diagnostics is commissioned
- the beamline optics is analysed, and the rms beam parameters are measured
- a prototype Laser Wire is tested.

Session 3: Pulsed LINACs: Spallation sources (chair: Willem Blokland - SNS)

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Experience from J-PARC LINAC commissioning

Akihiko Miura, J-PARC, Japan

The J-PARC started the beam commissioning in 2006 and achieved 181 MeV in 2007. The user experimental operation to generate neutrons in December 2008. The user experimental operation has continued with the exception of intervals due to the gigantic earthquake, hadron facility accident and neutron target failure.

In J-PARC linac, a number of beam monitor types have been used, such as the beam position monitor (BPM) for beam orbit correction, slow current transformer (SCT) for the beam current measurement, fast current transformer (FCT) that was used to tune the phase and voltage of the acceleration field, and transverse profile monitor (wire scanner monitor) to mitigate the transverse mismatching. In addition, BLMs are required to identify the local beam loss and are part of an alert system that protects the linac against an activation.

As recent progress, a carbon nanotube (CNT) wire is employed for the transverse profile monitors in low-energy part to prevent from wire break down. CNT wire showed excellent performance compared with the presently employed carbon fibre. In addition, prediction of over-heating by the secondary electron emission

is presented. Bunch-shape monitor utilisation for longitudinal tuning and investigation on the failure of RF power supply is also presented.

Beam profile taken by CNT wire and carbon fibre.

Commissioning and initial operating experience with the CSNS Linac

Peng Yun, CSNS-CAS, Beijing, China

The Front-end and DTL1-4 have been fully commissioned, the primary design goals concerning I_{peak} & $I_{average}$, transverse emittance and beam energy have been achieved. The DTL output energy design values, measured by phase scan method, agrees well with that measured by the time-of-flight method. Beam transmission efficiency and beam loss are well optimised. More work needs to be done on the halo formation mechanism and mitigation method.

Simulated and measured transverse emittance.

ESS beam commissioning experience commissioning results

Ryoichi Miramoto, ESS, Lund, Sweden

The presentation started with an overview of the ESS linac, its plan and the status of Beam Commissioning (BC). It followed up giving some highlights, focusing on diagnostics for the commissioning of the source and LEBT. The superconducting proton linac of ESS, with a normal-conducting injector up to 90 MeV and no accumulator ring, features design parameters of a 5 MW power, 2 GeV energy, 62.5 mA peak current, a long pulse length of 2.86 ms, and relatively low repetition rate of 14 Hz. This pulse length and repetition rate are required by neutron instruments and thus have a higher priority than the high peak current during BC and initial operations. Due to a tight schedule, the ESS opted not to use a test-bench after the BC of the source and LEBT. This decision is in line with the aforementioned priority in the duty factor from the neutron instruments.

The ESS source and LEBT went through an off-site beam commissioning at INFN-LNS (the in-kind provider) and were re-commissioned at the ESS site. The source is a microwave-discharge type, and the LEBT is a magnetic type with two solenoids and two dipole correctors per plane. Five types of diagnostics were available during the BC: beam current monitor (BCM), Faraday cup (FC), Doppler detector, fluorescence-based non-invasive profile monitor (NPM), and the Allison scanner type emittance meter (EMU). The characterisation of peak current and pulse shape was successfully performed: the source proves to be easily

The ESS diagnostics in the

adjustable and multiple configurations meeting specifications of the peak current (~ 90 mA out of the source and ~ 70 mA out of the LEBT) and flatness ($\pm 2\%$) were established. The Doppler detector confirmed a good proton fraction of 80-85% in the source current (with respect to the specified $>75\%$) during the early Phase of the off-site BC, when placed right after the source. After the LEBT was installed and it was placed between the solenoids, interpretation of the fraction measurement became less straightforward. The emittance was measured with the EMU between the solenoids and out of the LEBT. The NPM, installed at two locations, provided an additional and prompt way of estimating the beam properties between the solenoids. During the BC at the ESS site, all emittance measurements result in $\sim 0.4 \pi$ mm mrad ($\sim 10\%$ level agreement among locations and methods) for the aforementioned current case, with respect the specified $\sim 0.25 \pi$ mm mrad, and its major cause is still unknown. Moreover, during the BC at the ESS site, a large trajectory error with an estimated peak offset of ~ 4 mm, was observed prior to applying corrections. The NPMs were additionally used as position monitors and having them at two locations allowed to estimate the angular offset out of the source and tilts of both solenoids (likely internal tilts of the coils). Overall, the prepared diagnostics was sufficient to perform required characterisations and no need of an additional type of diagnostics was identified. What is being improved for future BC steps and operations is the whole chain from making a measurement and acquiring and processing data. Finally, to address beam related issues such as the emittance and trajectory, ESS is evaluating a test-stand for a source and LEBT.

Warm and cold LINAC commissioning

Alexander Aleksandrov, SNS, ORNL, Oak Ridge, USA

The SNS linac was successfully commissioned and ramped up for the design beam power in about six years. The baseline diagnostics were, in general, sufficient for all commissioning stages, though many improvements were done over that period. The SNS linac design proved to be very robust with large tuning margins. Beam Position and Phase Monitors are major tool for linac tuning after maintenance periods or when linac configuration has to be changed e.g., if some SRF cavities have to run at lower amplitude or even removed. Beam Loss Monitors are major tool for empirical loss minimisation at high power. We have not found yet good ways of using measured RMS beam parameters for linac tuning or operation. Motivation and direction for future SNS diagnostics development is to enable a knowledge-based loss control.

RF amplitude acceptable range is much larger than expected.

- **Session 4: Pulsed LINACs: Spallation sources (chair: Andreas Reiter - GSI)**

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Experiences from medical LINAC commissioning

Bernhard Schlitt, GSI, Darmstadt, Germany

After pilot projects at research institutes like HIMAC at NIRS and GSI started patient treatments using heavy ion beams in the 1990s, a growing number of dedicated clinical centres for ion beam therapy of cancer patients were built during the last two decades in Japan, Europe, and China, mainly applying carbon ion beams. About a dozen dedicated centres are in operation worldwide and eight additional centres are currently under construction or in planning stage. To reduce the footprint of these synchrotron facilities as well as operating expenses and effort, compact linac injectors operated at about 200 MHz – comprising at least one or two electron cyclotron resonance (ECR) ion sources, a radio-frequency quadrupole accelerator (RFQ), and an interdigital H-mode (IH-type) drift tube linac – were developed and built at NIRS in Japan and at GSI in Germany (in close cooperation with the Institute of Applied Physics IAP at Frankfurt University) and were industrialized later. A brief report about the 7 MeV/u, 217 MHz linac injector developed by GSI and IAP as well as the commissioning stages at HIT in Heidelberg, Germany, and at CNAO in Pavia, Italy, was presented.

RFQ beam tests were performed at IAP and at GSI prior to installation on site to check RFQ performance and to prepare the RFQ to match the beam requirements at IH-DTL injection. On site at HIT and CNAO, a staged

commissioning of the linac injectors was performed utilizing individual beam diagnostic test benches behind each injector section, i.e. behind ion sources and LEBT, behind the RFQ, and after the IH-DTL. All test benches comprised slit-grid beam emittance measurements (at CNAO, along the LEBT and at RFQ injection also slits and wire scanners for enhanced angular acceptance) as well as SEM profile grids, beam current transformers, and a Faraday cup. The test benches behind the RFQ and DTL sections, respectively, comprised also a set of three ring-shaped capacitive pick-ups (so-called phase probes) for bunch measurements and for accurate time-of-flight beam energy measurements. An improved beam characterization and optimized beam matching at RFQ injection was achieved at CNAO by using a very compact emittance chamber placed at the exact RFQ injection point and by RFQ acceptance measurements using probe beams with much smaller emittances than the nominal beams. Severe problems with beam steering, that occurred behind the last LEBT solenoid and behind the RFQ during HIT commissioning, as well as a reduced RFQ performance could be successfully mitigated in that way at CNAO. The working points of RFQ and IH-DTL were defined by the results of the beam commissioning (in particular, by phase and amplitude scans) in order to achieve optimized beam quality and linac transmission. Also the RF plunger settings of the IH-DTL were optimized with respect to beam quality. Finally, the design beam quality and currents were achieved at CNAO.

Analysis of Low and Medium Energy Beams at HIT

Rainer Cee, HIT, Heidelberg, Germany

The Heidelberg Ion Beam Therapy Centre (HIT) is a synchrotron based medical accelerator facility for the treatment of cancer patients with protons and ions. Since the first treatment in November 2009 more than 6500 patients have been irradiated with protons or carbon ions.

Profile grids and phase probes are routinely used for monitoring the LINAC-beam properties. The obtained data serve as reference and permit us to investigate the beam behavior prior to failures. The goal is to have an early-warning system by comparison of beam patterns with previous occurrences.

Since 2010 HIT operates a test bench for ion source and RFQ research and development. The setup is similar to the LEBT in our medical accelerator. In the last few years, we have measured several ion sources (ECR, EBIS) and the RFQ accelerator from our spares inventory. Since 2013 the test bench serves as a common low energy beamline of Siemens Healthcare and HIT with components from both partners. In 2019 we have characterized the spare RFQ of Siemens. The output beam was analyzed with respect to its energy via the time-of-flight (ToF) method based on three phase probes. The diagnostic line is also equipped with a profile grid, a beam transformer and a Faraday cup. We were particularly interested in the particle transmission and the RF working point at design output energy (400 keV/u). The measured transmissions (H_3^+ : 57%; $^{12}C^{4+}$: 84%) turned out to be better than for the HIT spare RFQ which translates into a factor of 1.7 for the $^{12}C^{4+}$ output current and a moderate current increase for H_3^+ . The RF power working point was close to 180 kW for both ions.

We have also experimented with our proprietary pepper pot device and evaluated the measured 4D emittance data with our tool Pepper Pot Evaluation Programme (PePE). From this analysis, we are able to generate a corresponding 4D particle distribution. To increase its active area a pepper pot device with new layout is under development. We plan to install the pepper pot into the LEBT and use the measured beam distributions for the design of a new RFQ with high transmission.

Contributions by: R. Cee, C. Dorn, E. Feldmeier, T. Haberer, A. Peters, J. Schreiner, T. Winkelmann, HIT GmbH, Heidelberg, Germany; O. Chubarov, A. Robin, Siemens Healthcare GmbH, Erlangen, Germany.

- **Session 5: Pulsed LINAC's: Injectors I (chair: Federico Roncarolo - CERN)**

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Status of the High Current Injector Programme at IUAC, New Delhi, India

Gerald Rodrigues, Inter University Accelerator Centre, New Delhi, India

The super conducting LINAC at the Inter University Accelerator Centre, New Delhi, is presently fed with a Tandem accelerator. This Tandem will be replaced by an RFQ and DTL linac to deliver higher beam currents.

The on-going High Current Injector Programme consists in the construction of the new LINAC injector, which consists of an ECR source, LEBT, RFQ, MEBT and two DTL cavities. It aims for a significant enhancement of the performances of the whole facility. The beam commissioning successfully reached the goal of accelerating up to the first two DTL cavities ion species with low A/q . The typical transmission values of 20% (DC beam) and 32% (bunched beam) along the Tandem accelerator have been already improved by the 25% and 36% values achieved with the new linac at the RFQ exit. It is believed that this could be further improved by adding dedicated diagnostics at the RFQ entrance, RFQ exit and DTL entrance.

The beam-based linac optimisation was carried out according to rigorous procedures. It was time consuming due to the high number of tuneable accelerator components. A lot of effort was put in studying the optics and comparing the results to the predicted values. Repeating the optimisation over time resulted to be very relevant to study the overall machine stability.

In the near future, the higher level RF power tests will be carried out for the RFQ and DTL cavities, which aims at improving the overall transmission at the DTL exit.

Linac4 Commissioning Strategy

Jean-Baptiste Lallement, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland

Since the end of the second LHC long shutdown (LS2), i.e. from the beginning of 2021, the H^- LINAC4 replaced proton LINAC2 (operated since 1978!) as source of protons for the whole CERN complex.

While details about instrumentation were discussed in another workshop contribution by J.Tan, this presentation consisted in a comprehensive summary of the commissioning strategy and experience.

H^- ions generated by a cesiated ion source, are accelerated from 45 keV to 160 MeV and stripped to protons before injection into the Proton Synchrotron Booster (PSB). The linac, after the RFQ is composed of 3 families of normal conducting RF cavities (DTL, CCDTL and PIMS).

The machine commissioning, lasted several years. At different stages during its construction different (temporary) diagnostic benches were developed for validating the source, the RFQ (3 MeV) and the first DTL (12 MeV) in a laboratory test stand. Later on, the accelerator was moved to the tunnel and then at the LINAC4 tunnel where the commissioning of the 50 MeV and 107 MeV acceleration used a modified diagnostics bench. These test benches were extremely useful to perform measurements not possible later with permanent installed diagnostics (like emittance via slit-grid at 45keV, 3MeV and 12 MeV) and validate diagnostics later used at higher energies (like BPMs for ToF measurements). At higher energies the beam commissioning was ensured by the permanently installed diagnostics.

At every commissioning stage the diagnostics and the procedures systematically put in place allowed for the validation of the RF cavities and beam optics, but also to discover 'classical' hardware faults as magnetic elements polarity inversions. One of the key elements for the machine validation was the systematic comparison between experimental measurements and beam dynamics (longitudinal and transverse) models.

This included numerical simulation for back tracking (via the models) particle distributions from high energy measurements to lower energy initial conditions.

After the successful acceleration to 160 MeV and transport through the new line towards the PSB, a revised planning for its connection resulted in the great chance for more than two years of standalone operation periods as 'reliability' runs interleaved by shutdown periods used for maintenance. This was also very useful for learning about the whole machine, including its diagnostics.

This contribution summarizes the LINAC4 experience, with key points useful for comparison to other similar linac commissioning experiences and potentially helpful for future projects:

1. LINAC design-wise:

- no major surprises in transverse planes: frozen focusing channel above 3 MeV.
- Solid design and precise machining of the RF cavities.
- Very good predictions from simulation codes (Travel-CERN, TraceWin-CEA).

2. Today, after so many machine restarts and setting-up, the linac operation and performance mainly rely on:

- Beam Current Transformers, for transmission optimisation and machine protection
- Time of Flight measurements via BPMs
- Bunch shape monitors (as a validation after the PIMS, more can be done in the transfer-line).
- Profile measurements along the machine and in the 2 dedicated measurement lines.

3. Beam stability and performance mainly depend on RF and low energy front-end.

4. All efforts for the 3-12 MeV dedicated diagnostics stand (then repeated in the LINAC4 tunnel) were extremely useful.

Development of CW heavy ion linac at IMP (normal-conducting)

Xuejun Yin, IMP, Lanzhou, China

- The SSC-Linac is a cw heavy ion linac designed to act as the new injector for the Separated Sector Cyclotron (SSC) built at HIRFL to improve the overall facility efficiency and performance. It replaces the injector cyclotron and allows for significantly higher beam currents. It consists of an electron-cyclotron-resonance ion source (ECR) followed by a 4-rod RFQ and three IH-DTLs (operating frequency 53.7 MHz) operated in cw mode. For the moment the new linac was successfully commissioned with two IH-DTL operational, allowing accelerating heavy ions to 0.58 MeV/u.
- In 2020 the linac in connection with the SSC accelerates various ion species (such as $^{78}\text{Kr}^{13+}$, $^{129}\text{Xe}^{22+}$, $^{209}\text{B}^{32+}$) and, after acceleration in the cyclotron to 5.97 MeV/u, extract them to various experimental lines. The linac transmission reached 86.5% and provided beam for 3617 hours within year 2020. The average beam intensity extracted from the SSC was about one order of magnitude higher compared to the operation with the injector cyclotron. To achieve the present operational performances, it is worth mentioning the action of the pre-buncher (operated at 13.417 MHz) installed in the LEBT. It is designed to increase the longitudinal capture efficiency, which reached 86% as expected for beam dynamics calculations. In a second stage, the linac will be equipped with the 3rd IH-DTL, thus allowing increasing the particle energy to 1.025 MeV/u.
- During construction and commissioning in a temporary laboratory setup, the beam at the RFQ exit was characterised in terms of intensity, transmission and emittance by means of a set of slits, a wire scanner and a Faraday cup. Similar diagnostics, complemented by an ionisation profile monitor, was successfully used at the exit of DTL1. In addition, the absolute energy was determined via ToF using stripline BPMs. The energy spread of different ion species was measured at the RFQ and DTL1 exit by inserting a target with an angle to the beam path and measuring (with a PIN detector) the resultant Rutherford scattered ions.
- In its final configuration at the SSC hall, the linac is equipped with permanent diagnostics in the LEBT, MEBT and HEBT (after the DTLs), such as wire scanners, Faraday cups, beam current transformers, strip line and button BPMs. This allowed to characterize beam intensity, phase, transverse emittance for various ion species.

- **Session 6: Pulsed LINAC's: Injectors II (chair: Oliver Kester - TRIUMF)**

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BNL Experiences for 200 MeV H⁻ Linac

Deepak Raparia, BNL, Brookhaven, USA

The BNL 200 MeV linac was built and commissioned in 1970 and is the backbone of the proton injection for AGS and the RHIC facility. In recent time the major fraction of the beam is delivered to the medical isotope production facility BLIP.

Since 1970, the linac has gone through several upgrades. In 1982 switching to H⁻ operation increased the intensity in the AGS, while decreasing the linac output overall. In 1989 switching to an RFQ pre-injector provided higher reliability and lower cost of operations. The changes in 1996 included shorting the 35 keV LEBT by removing diagnostics and adding a permanent magnet quad (PMQ) in the flange of the RFQ at the high energy end to better match the beam. These changes resulted in a 50% higher beam peak current and about 45% lower emittance.

In 2010, the medium energy beam line length was reduced to 70 cm from 7 meters, resulting in an emittance reduction for high current by a factor of 4 and for the polarised H⁻ by a factor of 2. The reduction in emittance for polarised H⁻ was translated into emittance reduction in RHIC by 25% at collision energy and 30% increase in BLIP average current. BNL has planned to further upgrade the linac for higher average current (250 μA) and energies up to 800 MeV.

For energy measurements in the linac a laser profile monitor is used to strip the H- and energy analyse the electrons in a retarding grid analyser. For an efficient beam transport in the LEBT, space charge neutralisation is important. The neutralisation time is about 100 microseconds. For the long pulses, used in BNL operation, a magnetic LEBT is advantageous, therefore solenoid lenses are used. Experiments with Xe-gas in the LEBT demonstrate increased peak beam current and faster neutralisation times.

LINAC4 diagnostics experience during commissioning

Jocelyn Tan, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland

Beam commissioning is the most interesting time for equipment specialists and an opportunity to pinpoint teething issues and take mitigation actions. That's also true for the CERN Linac4 commissioning that started in the early 2010's. LINAC4 has an impressive set of beam diagnostics devices installed along the accelerator and the transfer line for safe, reliable and efficient operation. For the staged commissioning a movable test bench has been used comprising transverse and longitudinal beam parameter measurement capabilities.

As in other low energy linacs, space constraints plague the beam instrumentation positioning. Between the tanks, one BPM and one quad are placed and in the DTL to CCDTL section a BPM and an BCT are available. The BCT must have a large dynamic range to cope with multi-user requests: resolution 0.5 mA, gating between 50 ns to 600 microseconds. The BCT serves as LINAC4 watchdogs by comparing the intensity at various locations of the linac and allowing transmission efficiency calculation, by high loss detection, and acting as beam interlock in case of high losses or bad transmission.

BPMs are the 'Swiss army knife', used to optimise the chopper rise time, investigate the beam phase and energy, and allow for fast optimisation. Bunch shape monitors (BSM) at LINAC4 use secondary electrons produced by a tungsten wire moved into the beam and a streak camera setup. The team used the BSMs and bunchers for longitudinal emittance reconstruction / tomography. The team could also demonstrate the effect of beam loading (and compensation) on the bunch shape and achieved the very first proof of principle of energy modulation around 160MeV for future high intensity beams in the PSB.

The presentation concluded with transverse emittance and beam profile measurements using SEM grids for instance, and with BLM (LHC types) that are used for the machine protection. In SEM grids, wire signals are a balance between negative charge (stripped electrons stopped) and positive charge (secondary emission + p eventually stopped) and depend on the wire material properties. It could be shown that Tungsten is not suitable for low energy, Carbon is preferred at up to 50 MeV. Laser profile and emittance meter has been presented and is an interesting alternative for methods relying on material intercepting the beam.

Commissioning of Low-Energy Linacs

Andreas Reiter, GSI, Darmstadt, Germany

Andreas Reiter presented experiences collected during the commissioning of low-energy linacs, the 7 MeV/u injector linacs of HIT (Heidelberg Ion-Beam Therapy Centre) and CNAO (Centro Nazionale di Adroterapia Oncologica), and several GSI linacs such as the 11 MeV/u UNILAC, the 4 MeV/u HITRAP decelerator, 1.9 MeV/u CW Demonstrator, and the 300 keV/u CRYRING RFQ injector. A significant number of low energy linacs.

Some focus was on the on different measurements with capacitive ring pickups at the test benches inf the different commissioning stages, which have been introduced. In preparation of time-of-flight measurement,

expected pickup signal and sophisticated shape analysis and TOF calculation have been discussed and compared. The inter-tank phase probes have also been used as 'emergency' AC current transformer.

Beam energy measurements were presented for both, the 400 keV/u RFQ and 7 MeV/u IH-DTL linacs. For the RFQ with internal rebuncher, beam energy stability has been measured via TOF using three phase probes. An attempt was made to determine the position of the time focus, that ideally should be located in the first gap of the following IH-DTL linac. Confidence was gained that the internal rebuncher voltage was setup quite well during initial RFQ commissioning at GSI.

Further topics are energy loss measurements in Carbon stripping foils, estimation of the momentum dispersion of the 7 MeV/u IH-DTL, and a simple approach to track the beam energy during parameter variations, like RF power scans, that are commonly performed during commissioning.

Session 7: Front-ends, targets and future facilities: Front-ends (Chair: Liu Yong - KEK)

Bilbao injector beam commissioning

Ibon Bustinduy, ESS-Bilbao, Bilbao, Spain

The Medium Energy Beam Transfer (MEBT) of the European Spallation Source (ESS) is developed by ESS-Bilbao as an in-kind contribution. A versatile and in-house developed injector was also scheduled based on it, which consists of a proton ion source, LEBT and a shorter (3.2m, with lower injection energy of 45 keV instead of 75 keV) and possibly non-brazing RFQ. The RFQ Segment 1 (aka proof of principle) was finished and S2-S4 machining is on-going.

There are two solenoids and three diagnostic boxes in the LEBT. The first box is equipped with an AC Current Transformer (ACCT1), a double-wire Wire Scanner (WS1) and a retractile beam collimator (BC) to create a pencil beam. The second box contains a second ACCT2, a second WS (WS2), a quartz window for fluorescence measurements and a retractile beam shutter that protects the quartz. The two wires of the WS are at 45° from the horizontal and vertical directions. A Princeton Instrument CCD camera complements the quartz window in the exit port of the diagnostic box, for 2D profile photographs and pepper-pot measurements. The camera is also used to record the Beam Induced Fluorescence (BIF) by mounting it in the side port of the first box.

LEBT STAGES#1 uses the first two diagnostic boxes and the first solenoid in between, aiming at optimizing or studying the transmission, extraction gap, B and h/v steering characterized, h/v Beam Profile analysis, Beam Specimen identification, Fringe field effects, Kr Neutralization and h/v Emittance. Scintillator Quartz in the second box was employed to identify plasma configuration families. And plasma shape is found well preserved even after the 45kV electrode shape extraction system. Ultrafast pictures were taken to identify various plasma distribution modes.

Back streamed electrons (1) captured by solenoid magnetic field and over-focusing solenoid effect (2) were observed with transmission measurement with ACCTs, as shown in Fig.7.1a. Composition of H^+ , H_2^+ and likely H_3^+ was analysed, as shown in Fig.7.1b.

Figure 7.1a Transmission measurement.

Figure 7.1b Composition analysis.

The solenoid field-maps were measured with a triple-axis hall probe, mounted on a computer numerical control (CNC), but the fringe field could not be measured due to test bench limitation. IBSIMU+ TRACEWIN simulations employing accurate 3D field-maps help to understand the experimental characterization of the beam profiles for different solenoid magnetic configurations.

Beam Profile and emittance characterization for different solenoid configurations were obtained with calibrated reconstruction algorithm. Successful complete Bilbao system integration tests were done in collaboration with ESS control and Diagnostics team. There are also on-going improvements such as FC system, second solenoid, coupler, RF, etc. Deep learning techniques are developed to assist operation.

LIPAc injector commissioning and RFQ transverse emittance measurements

Benoit Bolzon, CEA/Saclay, Saclay, France

The linear IFMIF prototype accelerator (LIPAc) aims to operate in Rokkasho Fusion Institute a 125 mA CW deuteron beam at 9 MeV to validate the concept of IFMIF. This accelerator is composed of an electron cyclotron resonance (ECR) ion source, a low energy beam transport (LEBT), a 175 MHz RFQ to 5 MeV, a medium energy beam transport section designed to optimize the D^+ injection into a superconducting radio-frequency (SRF) linac to 9 MeV, a high energy beam transport line with a diagnostic plate, and a beam dump.

Two AC current transformers (ACCTs) are installed at the end of the injection cone before the RFQ and just downstream the RFQ respectively, to measure the RFQ transmission. An Allison scanner is chosen as the emittance measurement unit (EMU), to measure the beam distribution in the (y, y') phase space. Due to cylindrical symmetry, the emittance should be identical in both planes. It is planned in a near future to do such a measurement in the horizontal plane, by tilting the EMU by 90° . Considering the high beam power, beam profilers based on the fluorescence of residual gas have been chosen. It is also possible to determine the proportions of the different species composing the beam using Doppler-shifted spectroscopy. A CCD camera is installed at the focal plane of a spectrometer with an angle of 20° relatively to the beam direction.

Fig. 7.2a Beam emittance measured at RFQ entrance.

Fig. 7.2b RFQ 130 mA CW run with no sparks.

CMOS camera after SOL1

Fig. 7.2c CMOS camera after SOL1

Emittance measured with 2.5 MeV H⁺ beam at 22 mA (800 μs, 1 Hz) in 2019

Fig. 7.2d Measured RFQ transverse Emittance.

Commissioning results show that the injector can provide at low duty cycle a 100 keV D⁺ beam of 140 mA with “adequate” emittance / Twiss parameters for RFQ injection. Therefore, a 12 mm ϕ PE was used to ensure enough extracted current. When duty cycle increases to CW, the extraction system of the injector suffered from several sparks (phase A2). Two campaigns in CW were performed in 2019 with PE of lower diameters (9 and 10 mm) to try to avoiding sparks even if the extracted current is lower. Results showed that these electrodes can be used for RFQ injection from low DC up to CW for a stable total extracted current either with $I_{ext}= 95\text{-}100$ mA for 9 mm PE ϕ , or $I_{ext}= 130$ mA for 10 mm PE ϕ , as shown in Fig. 7.2b and Fig. 7.2c. Another campaign was planned for nominal current required for LIPAc (140 mA of D⁺ at the RFQ entrance) with an 11 mm ϕ PE but it had to be postponed due to Covid-19.

The transverse emittance after RFQ was measured successfully. Good agreement was found between measurements and simulations, as shown in Fig. 7.2d.

6D measurements on a test stand

Kiersten Ruisard, SNS ORNL, Oak Ridge, USA

The Beam Test Facility (BTF) was originally built to verify the spare RFQs at the Spallation Neutron Source (SNS). It becomes a test stand version of SNS injector, which has unique capabilities of measuring the full 6D phase space, studying halo development under different match conditions. It can help to characterize the beam at several standard deviations beyond the rms values, as is necessary to predict beam losses in high-power accelerators.

The first-ever full and direct measurement of a 6D beam distribution was done at the SNS BTF (published in 2018). This measurement proved that the assumption of uncorrelated planes is incorrect for the SNS beam at the RFQ exit, as shown in Fig.7.3a.

Fig. 7.3a First 6D measurement discovered correlation between energy and transverse dimensions.

Since then work has focused on two questions: understanding why the beam has correlation between the planes, and understanding the effect on downstream evolution, particularly in the context of effect on halo predictions. The failure of models to predict halo/tail populations means they cannot assist in loss control in high power accelerators. Fig. 7.3b shows the preliminary simulation results with inter-plane correlations compared with original uncorrelated assumption with discrepancy in rms values.

Fig. 7.3b Preliminary simulation of SNS linac (MEBT+DTL) with/without inter-plane correlations.

Studies show that correlation between the planes is driven by space charge, and the hollowing is the signature of charge redistribution. These answers are reproduced in self consistent RFQ simulation with PARMTEQ. Yet it will be not easy to explain the mechanism within RFQ, as well as the issues like whether it is ubiquitous for high current RFQs and how to model and diagnose.

Another interesting issue is how to mitigate “curse of dimensionality” for 6D measurement. A typical 4D measurement could take as long as 14 hours, noting the original took 32 hours with low-resolution (~ 10~20 pts /dimension) and low-dynamic range. Smart scan to stay within small beam volume and dimension-reducing with 2D BSM are considered to mitigate the curse of dimensionality. New reconfiguration with straight layout is planned to improves beam control.

- **Session 8: Front-ends, targets and future facilities: Targets and future facilities (chair: Concepcion Oliver Amoros - CIEMAT)**

- **Spallation Neutron Source Target Commissioning**

Willem Blokland, SNS ORNL, Oak Ridge, USA

SNS uses a liquid mercury filled stainless steel target to generate neutrons for material research from a 1 GeV pulsed proton beam. The impact of the proton beam leads to tensile pressure waves that cavitate the mercury and deform the vessel by 10 - 500 μe on wall. This damages the target vessel over time and the target has to be preventative replaced two to three times a year. Unexpected failures in the past and future power upgrades have pushed us to install strain sensors in the target to provide data to use to better understand the target response.

The nose of target is coated in an $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{:Cr}$ luminescent coating to observe with a camera the proton beam's centre and peak density to make sure we don't damage the target by steering beam off centre or with a too high density. The coating is scanned for uniformity with the first beam on the target using a script that adjusts the steering of the beam while making sure the imaging system takes data. During this scan, test patches with new $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{:Cr}$ mixtures are also scanned for initial luminescence response. Next, we measure the strain response of beam pulses of different intensities, and with different helium gas injection flows. The gas injection reduces the strain on the target making it possible to handle high beam powers. To quickly setup the accelerator for the different intensity pulses, we created an application that automatically prepares setup parameters such as the RF feedforward loops and the chopper settings. We compare this strain data with simulation results to improve the simulation model. It takes up to one shift of 8 hours to complete the commissioning of the target. After these first beam pulses, neutron production for the experiments is started and we continue to periodically measure the strain and the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{:Cr}$ luminescence response.

Strain measurements at different power and helium flow levels measured at SNS.

Instrumentation for beam commissioning: available tools and future needs

Steve Lidia, FRIB Michigan State University, East Lansing, USA

The Facility for Rare Isotope Beams (FRIB) has been established to service the needs of the low energy nuclear physics community. The accelerator is based on low-beta, continuous-wave, superconducting RF linac technology, and operates at the intensity frontier for heavy ion facilities with ultimate, average beam power of 400 kW. The successful commissioning activities have demonstrated the flexibility of the ECR ion source and Front End beamline to deliver high quality beam to the linac, which has demonstrated full gradient and acceleration up to the design value of 200 MeV/u.

Different challenges related to beam diagnostics and instrumentation are the handling of intense and low energy ion beams with multi-charge-state beam dynamics, with A/Q ranging from 3 to 7, the requirement of beam losses below 1 W/m, the need for a robust, fast machine protection system or the 400 kW heavy ion beam target.

A complete set of Front End diagnostics and instrumentation have been utilized for beam commissioning and optimizing beam transport. In particular, it should be emphasized the multiple roles played by the profile monitors in the Front End, the network of beam position monitors and beam loss monitors in the linac. The high power target thermal imaging system allows the beam monitoring on target and dump, detecting variations in position, distribution and intensity by measuring the target temperature.

The strategy behind design and implementation of instrumentation emphasizes a common approach for hardware and software integration. New diagnostic functionalities have been implemented since commissioning, enhancing the overall facility performance, ease of tuning, and availability. Automatic linac tuning routines that utilize time-of-flight measurement software enable to tune nearly 150 independent cavities over a single shift period, with 100% beam transmission.

Moving from commissioning to operations requires a change in strategy, demanding new developments of diagnostic and prognostic monitoring to fully develop the facility capabilities. Additional non-interceptive diagnostics will be needed as the beam power will be higher. The faster turnaround between experiments and the consequent higher availability implies reducing dependency on interceptive (and slow) measurements, developing virtual diagnostics. The dependency on system experts will be reduced during operation, incorporating input from operation early and often, simplifying and integrating user interfaces and giving the operators the tools they need. New techniques will be implemented to help build prognostics and improve scientific productivity.

Commissioning Plans of the 5 MW DONES facility

Ivan Podadera, CIEMAT, Madrid, Spain

DONES facility is a future facility, based on the IFMIF design, which is being designed by EUROFUSION since 2015. Its main goal is to provide a high flux of fusion-like neutrons to create a materials properties database for future fusion reactors, like DEMO. The main differences between DONES and IFMIF designs are the use of one single accelerator, instead of two, and several other updates in the design to reduce the cost and the technical risk.

The DONES accelerator is based on an ion source and LEPT, a 10 m RFQ, a 2 m MEBT with two re-buncher cavities and five magnets, a superconducting LINAC based on five cryomodels (two

equipped with low-beta cavities and the three last ones with high-beta cavities), and a HEBT equipped with multipole magnets to shape the beam for a rectangular footprint in the lithium screen.

The commissioning procedure is based on the optimisation of the project schedule and machine protection. Moreover, the commissioning of the prototype IFMIF accelerator, LIPAC is one of the main assets for the definition of the DONES commissioning. The one of DONES is made of four main stages. During the first one, the ion source and LEBT will be commissioned up to CW, during the second one the RFQ and MEBT will be commissioned up to 10% DC and nominal current, while in parallel the last four cryomodules will be installed to start the hardware commissioning. The third stage will consist of the beam commission of the complete cryomodule in pulsed mode, using the beam dump line for beam characterisation. The fourth and last stage is the transport of the beam down to the target, first in low duty cycle and ramping up to CW.

Conventional beam instrumentation is installed in the main beamline to ensure the high availability and protection of the machine. However, some R&D is still required for the diagnostics in some areas: micro beam losses in the SRF, beam losses along the accelerator, as well as transverse beam profile monitoring in the SRF LINAC, multipoles region and target footprint.

Along the SRF LINAC it is a real challenge to monitor the transverse profile in the cryomodules or in the warm sections. Space has been reserved for a multi-wire grid in the warm sections, and a preliminary design exists, although the simulations show only beams up to 25 mA / 50 us could be accepted by a tungsten wire (20 um diameter), due to the small beam sizes.

In the target footprint, an assessment of the sources of light and the light yield was given. The results show that OTR is the best theoretical candidate since it avoids the profile distortion caused by the fluorescence of argon. An experimental campaign is being planned to verify the simulations. Finally, an RF pickup is being evaluated as a possible alternative for the protection of the target during operation.

MYRRHA RFQ commissioning

Angélique Gatera, SCK CEN MYRRHA, Mol, Belgium

The MYRRHA project at SCK CEN is an ADS composed of a sub-critical nuclear reactor driven by a 2.4 MW linear proton accelerator (600 MeV, 4 mA CW beam) as the final stage. The accelerator is being designed to achieve unprecedented reliability and availability, explaining the phased approach in its installation. The first phase currently ongoing until 2026 aims at demonstrating the fault compensation strategy for the 600 MeV linac on a 100 MeV linac test installation. This MYRRHA phase 1 accelerator, also referred to as MINERVA, will deliver a 100 MeV, 4 mA CW proton beam. The reliability requirement implies that the Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF) of the beam delivery must be > 250 h. The accelerated beam will be sent to a PTF (Proton Target Facility) for various applications including ISOL, fusion research and isotope production.

The front-end of the Linac's injector is composed of an ECR proton source, a 2m long LEBT (low energy beam transport line) and a four rods RFQ accelerating the beam to 1.5 MeV. During the LEBT beam commissioning, transverse emittance measurements were performed with Allison scanners,

analysing the beam quality injected into the RFQ and evaluating the Space Charge Compensation (SCC) effects on the beam. The source RF amplifier was upgraded to achieve a clean and stable beam current.

The commissioning of the RF system lasted about 2 years, spanning from individual tests on RFQ, SSA and LLRF to the operation of the full RF system with long run tests. After that, beam tests have been performed, with a comprehensive assessment of the beam transmission through the four rods RFQ. All the measured performances are according to expectations. The transmission at nominal power (110 kW, 44 kV) is 95%, being up to 98% for 125 kW (48 kV). It has been observed that RFQ transmission is not affected by space charge compensation with Argon injection in the LEBT. No problems have been found when pushing the duty cycle to CW.

The accelerated beam characterization, both in transverse and longitudinal planes, is expected in the coming months. The use of a dipole spectrometer will provide beam energy and energy spread measurements. The beam position will be measured by BPMs and a slit-grid emittance meter will reconstruct both transverse emittances. For the bunch shape reconstruction, a so-called Feschenko monitor, currently under procurement, will be used.

- **Session 9: Specific techniques for accelerator commissioning (chair: Victor Scarpine - Fermilab)**

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- **LINAC4 beyond classical control: experience from first tests of Machine Learning techniques applied to L4 modelling**

Verena Kain, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland

Numerical optimization and/or reinforcement learning are promising alternatives for efficient and flexible operation in case accelerator models are not available online, the models are incomplete or cannot be used for correction due to lack of instrumentation or the model not being invertible.

At CERN a generic optimization framework is being developed based on open source python libraries. Interface classes for various optimization problem types are provided together with a plug&play GUI for the control room. The most frequently used algorithms are COBYLA and BOBYQA. Examples of COBYLA on trajectory steering and chopping efficiency optimization at LINAC4 were shown. During CERN long shutdown 2 (LS2), reinforcement learning (RL) algorithms were extensively tested at the proton driven plasma wakefield test facility AWAKE as well as at LINAC4. Sample efficiency was one of the key criteria for choosing an appropriate RL algorithm. The CERN team tested Q-learning, actor-critic methods as well as model-based RL with dyna-Q learning. Trajectory steering was chosen as test case due to the high dimensionality of observation and actor space as well as the possibility of comparison with analytic methods (e.g. SVD). Very good results were achieved with all the algorithms. They are opening doors for many applications: training controllers on simulation instead of on the machine directly, learning the dynamics through interaction with the machine only and solving the control problem with model-predictive control or model-based RL, etc.

Convinced that these algorithms will play a major role in future control rooms, CERN is investing into an ML infrastructure next to the generic optimization framework. It will allow to store and

retrieve neural networks from within the accelerator control system. Many ML applications are in the making for the 2021 start-up of the CERN injector chain.

Beam loss (micromegas) instrumentation for LINAC commissioning

Laura Segui, CEA/Saclay, Saclay, France

A new kind of beam loss monitors (nBLM, neutron Beam Loss Monitors) have been developed in the last years to enlarge the sensitivity in the low energy regions of hadrons accelerators. Developed in collaboration between CEA Saclay and ESS being part of the ESS beam instrumentation systems, it has been designed to be sensitive to fast neutrons. Indeed, in the low energy regions only neutrons and gammas can escape from the interaction of the hadrons with the surrounding materials. Gammas coming from the RF however, represent an irreducible background that can limit the sensitivity to beam losses. The detectors proposed, based on the use of gaseous amplification structures called Micromegas, have a very good rejection capability between the signal produced by the neutrons and those from gammas.

The detection of the neutrons is performed in several steps: Firstly, charged particles are generated by nuclear reactions, Secondly, these charged particles will then ionize the gas in the detector, thirdly, gas ions and electrons will drift towards electrodes by an applied electric field, and, fourthly, then amplified by a second stage by applying a much stronger field. The detector is capable to detect event by event to increase the sensitivity to small beam losses, having a current amplifier on board of the detector directly. Moreover, the system can also operate in current mode to avoid saturation effects. Two complementary modules have been designed, on which the only differences are the neutron-to-charge-particle converter used and in one of them we surrounded by polyethylene to moderate the neutrons and increase its efficiency. Both modules operate in the same way and with the same electronics, being one more adapted to fast losses and the other to the monitoring of small losses and activation.

In this presentation the design of the detectors is shown as well as the discrimination of neutrons and gammas. In addition, detectors have been tested at LINAC4 where provoked losses were produced to be able to study the response of the nBLMs. The neutron rate detected in the nBLM is proportional to the loss level and we also prove the identification of gammas coming from the RF and neutrons from the beam.

Bunch shape monitors for hadron LINAC commissioning

Sergei Gavrilov, INR RAS, Moscow, Russia

Bunch shape, a longitudinal charge distribution in beam bunches, is one of the most important and interesting characteristics of a beam in ion linear accelerators (linacs). In case the accelerator operates with harmonic frequencies of the accelerating field for the high energy cavities, the information about the bunch shape becomes of special importance due to the changing of the longitudinal acceptance and the need of longitudinal beam matching.

Despite the variety of approaches, the only methods using low energy secondary electrons, emitted when the beam passes through a thin target, found practical application. This talk is a short review of well-known diagnostic device – Bunch Shape Monitor and based on the manufacturer's point of view and experience.

The principle of operation, some design features and variety of measurement results at different linac all over the world since 1988 up to the moment are described. Recent improvements (RF deflector with symmetric fields, magnetic shield and correctors) enable to achieve about 0.5° phase resolution for hundreds of MHz, which corresponds to 4 ps time resolution, however there are also new challenges such as further phase resolution improvement and non-interceptive measurements, which could make the monitor suitable for any existing and forthcoming linacs. The technology used for the Bunch Shape Monitor is now developed to such a stage, that the time spread related to the secondary electron emission (in the order of few ps) might now be the fundamental resolution limit.

- **Session 10: Company contributions to LINACs (chair: Peter Forck - GSI)**

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Experiences as a contractor for Linac design and production during on-site beam commissioning

Ulrich Ratzinger, University Frankfurt and Bevatech, Frankfurt, Germany

The participation of Bevatech in linac commissioning was reported in detail in case of the new HILAC for the NICA - project, at JINR Dubna, Russia. Results obtained during commissioning of the high charge state ion linac were discussed. The advantages and disadvantages of extra drift space in linacs for permanently installed beam diagnostic tools were discussed, and compromises were addressed. The success of close cooperation between Lab and company staff members during commissioning was pointed out. Generally, industrial partners can overtake the design and production of accelerator parts of known technology, while academic institutes can concentrate on R&D projects related to novel ideas.

The Bevatech GmbH, Frankfurt, hosted in the Frankfurt Innovation Centre, is specialised on ion linac accelerator cavities, diagnostics and controls. They are ready to support laboratories during design and up to the commissioning process at variable levels of cooperation – up to an overtake of full responsibility and project management for the whole linac.

LINAC production and commissioning from a company's perspective

Alexander Bechthold, NTG, Gelnhausen, Germany

NTG provides design, manufacture and commissioning of rf-cavities from a single source. Three major projects in the field are presented with particular focus on high power CW-RFQ cavities following a new 4-rod design with dipole compensation. The presentation demonstrates the interaction of different projects, how special techniques and methods emerge from similar tasks for different applications and finally apply to a variety of projects. Examples for produced cavities are depicted together with their mechanical and electrical quality assessment.

This mechanism is the driving force leading a medium-sized company into a specialised niche with complementary skills. In contrast, suppliers find themselves increasingly confronted with tenders packed with detailed specifications on engineering procedures to be followed on which they have no influence. The collaboration during the design phase already, to participate in the engineering process and the work planning, would help keep the diversity of specialised companies alive.